

4.2

DELIVERABLE

RECIPE HANDBOOK

Università di Scienze
Gastronomiche di Pollenzo
University of Gastronomic of Pollenzo

42 RECIPES

designed for European school canteens

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Abstract

This handbook contains **42 recipes** that have been specially designed for **use in European school canteens**.

The aim is to encourage the adoption of good, healthy, sustainable dishes. The recipes were conceived, designed and revised by school catering chefs from 12 European countries involved in the **SchoolFood4Change project**. These countries are Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Slovakia, Sweden and Hungary under the coordination of the University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo. This cookbook brings together different voices, skills and culinary cultures to support the design of nutritious and sustainable school menus.

It is intended for school catering chefs, dieticians, teachers, canteen staff and parents.

Not only that.

The manual is also a practical application of the principles and content of the *School Menu Design Handbook*, which was shared with chefs during online and in-person training sessions in Pollenzo in 2023 and 2024. As well as guiding the step-by-step creation of a dish, the recipe also serves as an integrated design and communication tool.

Keywords: recipes, school meal, school canteen, cooks, training, children food preferences, progressive food exposure, circular cooking.

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42 recipes

General introduction

by Fassio Franco, Povigna Carol, Bigi Matteo, Buracco Nabuel, Tecco Nadia

42 recipes for healthier and sustainable eating in schools

This manual brings together **42 recipes** designed and created for **European school canteens** with the aim of promoting the adoption and acceptability of good, healthy and sustainable food. The recipes have been conceived/created/modified by school catering chefs working in 12 European realities adhering to the **SchoolFood4Change** project and coming from Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Slovakia, Sweden and Hungary through the coordination of the University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo.

Not only that. The manual is also the concrete result of the application of the contents and principles collected in the *School Menu Design Handbook*, shared with chefs during online and in-presence training sessions at Pollenzo in 2023 and 2024.

The handbook stems from the need to bring together multiple voices, skills and culinary cultures with the aim of supporting the design of nutritious and conscious school menus by addressing other school catering chefs and other figures who are relevant both in the delivery of the service and in the food education process such as dietitians, teachers, canteen staff, procurers and last but not least parents. In fact the recipe in this context becomes a shared tool and acquires different meanings and usefulness for each of the figures mentioned above. In addition to being a tool that guides, through the illustration of the ingredients and the steps necessary for their transformation, the creation of a dish, the recipe is also a tool for integrated planning and communication.

It becomes the starting point and the first form of practical translation of the indications for a healthy and sustainable diet: the scientific knowledge of the principles governing the transformation processes and the functionalisation, in sensory terms and optimisation of each process converge in it.

The search for sensory enjoyment together with creativity and the principles of circular cooking bring together in the recipe the most suitable techniques to obtain the sensory characteristics most appreciated by children and young people on appearance, texture,

aroma and taste, acting as a tool to counteract the production of waste during consumption, and to reduce waste in the gastronomic transformation phases.

The recipe, through the ingredients, provides information on the nutritional value, making it possible to monitor key variables for a healthy and balanced diet such as the intake of sugars, fibre, saturated fats and salt, the correct portioning of the dish in terms of macro- and micronutrients, and its ability to be nutritionally and socio-culturally inclusive.

Through the recipe, it is possible to broaden the look at the sourcing of raw materials, considering provenance, seasonality, biodiversity, quality of ingredients, the method and environmental impacts of production, enhancing and communicating the choices made by the city in the procurement process. The recipe therefore communicates to the community how, through operational choices, the school meal can become a lever for change and support the ecological and protein transition.

It is a tool that can also become part of the process of food and taste education, in which the kitchen, the refectory and the schoolroom are not separate spaces and areas, but moments of an educational continuum, in which areas of integration and exchange are created, consistent with the principles of the Whole School Food Approach. The recipe as a platform to unite ingredients, dishes, menus, progressive display strategies, educational experiences in a coherent and shared pathway.

PROCESS AND READING GUIDE

In order to facilitate the use of the recipe as a multifunctional tool, as described above, and to facilitate a multilevel reading, the *Pollenzo Food Lab of the University of Gastronomic Sciences* developed a predefined recipe structure, which was shared with the cooks in the training course. The structure underwent some modifications after the exchange with the cooks trainers, and was used, firstly, to gather contributions from the different project contexts as an operational tool for the creation of healthy and sustainable recipes, and now, as a way of returning and disseminating the recipes in this manual.

The recipe template used is illustrated below, with a brief explanation of the different sections (**Recipe sample and how to read it**).

The 42 recipes collected have been divided into 6 chapters, each focusing on a specific topic.

1. Basic tools to design good

To reflect on how on the basis of the specific characteristics linked to sensory perception and closely related to the evidence on the appearance, texture and flavour of a dish, recipes, through appropriate design, can satisfy taste.

2. Balanced dishes

To provide recipes that offer a complete nutritional intake, in terms of the quantity and quality of the macro- and micro-nutrients involved in the design.

3. Protein transition

To incorporate alternative protein sources into recipes, through new proposals or the repurposing of well-known traditional meat dishes, using progressive exposure and camouflage strategies.

4. Adaptive recipes

To use modularity as a principle for adapting and proposing new recipes. It is possible to achieve the same end result simply by playing with variables such as special dietary requirements, seasonality and serving methods.

5. Cuisine and circularity

To design recipes incorporating the use of whole ingredients and creative recycling of raw materials often wasted in school canteens. To recover waste and optimise production flows without compromising the final taste.

6. Dishes for advanced tastes

To address those categories of dishes that, based on experience, pupils tend to reject the most. The focus is on soups, salads and fish dishes in particular, paying particular attention to the choice of ingredients, processing and serving methods to guide taste.

These topics were selected by the authors of the manual and the chefs participating in the SF4C project as they were considered representative of the most relevant challenges that school catering chefs themselves face on a daily basis to promote the adoption and acceptability of a planetary and healthy diet among students.

This selection was the outcome of the discussion held during the second in-person training course in September 2024 at the University of Gastronomic Sciences in Pollenzo.

Recipe sample and how to read it

NAME OF THE RECIPE

Recipe title

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

CITY AND COUNTRY

Which city did it come from and where is it served in schools.

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

GLUTEN FREE

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

VEGAN

2

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	-	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	-	(% of total)
Fibre Content	-	(grams)
Sodium	-	(grams)
Sugars	-	(grams)
Saturated Fats	-	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES/NO	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES/NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	n°
Upcycling Processes	YES/NO
Organic	YES/NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES/NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES/NO

TYPE OF DISH

Main Course

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

City and Country

RECIPE TITLE

The name given to the recipe.

TYPE OF DISH

The type of dish for which the recipe is being presented; pasta, soup, salad, burger, etc.

CITY AND COUNTRY

The origin of the recipe. Which city did it come from and where is it served in schools.

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

The time of year when the ingredients for the recipe are available, respecting seasonality.

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

An educational activity that can be combined with serving the dish to encourage acceptance.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUE

The message that the dish wants to convey and who is preparing it.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

The compatibility of the recipe with allergens, intolerances, and vegetarian and vegan diets.

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Each portion includes: energy, fiber, sugars, fats (saturated and polyunsaturated), salt, fruit and vegetable % and plant-based proteins.

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Environmentally relevant info like number of ingredients, whether they're organic or local, use of local varieties, biodiversity-friendly production and circular cooking.

INGREDIENT

The list of ingredients is in order of quantity, starting with the main one. NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one.

PARAMETRIC PERCENTAGE

The quantitative ratio between ingredients in percentage terms, considering the main ingredient as 100.

QUANTITY PER BATCH

The quantities of each ingredient used during preparation for school canteens. Here, the unit of measurement is expressed in kg, considering the large quantities involved.

QUANTITY PER PORTION

The quantities of each ingredient used during preparation expressed in grams.

NUTRITIONAL VALUE

For each ingredient, the energy value, fibre, sugar, saturated fat and salt content.

KITCHEN WASTE

For each ingredient, the percentage of waste generated during the cooking process is provided.

PREPARATION

The steps involved in making the recipe, including the production of semi-finished products, their storage and possible use in other preparations.

DIRECTIONS

Description of the process and steps for correctly preparing the recipe.

SERVICE LINE

How the dish is served in the canteen.

RECEPTION INFORMATION

Serving temperature and tips to make the dish more appealing, including through appropriate presentation.

NOTES FOR THE SERVICE

Notes and additional tips.

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Main Ingredient	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ingredient 15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION

Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Semi finished	-	-	-
(2) Semi finished	-	-	-
(3) Semi finished	-	-	-
(4) Semi finished	-	-	-
(5) Semi finished	-	-	-

DIRECTIONS

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1	2	3

1

2

3

Basic tools to design the good

This first chapter contains a collection of recipes that outline some of the basic principles and tools used to design and promote the acceptability of school meals. However, before we delve into these principles and tools, it is best to take a step back and ask ourselves what we mean by 'good'. As one of the most controversial and divisive concepts, the palatability of any food would seem to be an instinctively highly individual and subjective judgement based on each person's sensory and cognitive evaluations. This is true to some extent. However, in this context, 'good' is not purely an individual assessment, but rather one shared by people from different gastronomic cultures.

In this scenario, we are referring to food that is perceived as good because of its intrinsic characteristics, mainly its appearance, taste and texture, as well as its familiarity.

We therefore consider characteristics such as a sweet taste, a red or orange colour and certain textures that people tend to recognise as enjoyable.

Therefore, the recipes presented below have been grouped according to the following criteria:

- the ingredients chosen, such as the umami taste from mature cheese or the bright colours of pumpkin;
- the culinary processes used. For example, layering in the **Lentil lasagne** recipe serves to mask new flavours within a crunchy, creamy texture. Similarly, long cooking processes concentrate flavours in many of these recipes;

- the expected end result is also a factor, as seen with the **Autumn burger with coleslaw and potatoes** and **Winter galette with coral lentils, sweet potato and spices**, which have a round, familiar shape that is easy to eat with hands. Paying attention to these aspects is the first step towards a more individual and personal definition / construction of taste.

You can explore these topics in more depth by consulting the *Food Preferences* chapter of the *School Menu Design Handbook*, particularly pages 19–53.

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Malmö,
Sweden

Helen Nilsson, Louise Dahl Gottberg,
Tina Bowley, Andrea Razzaboni

**Autumn burger
with coleslaw and potatoes**

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Budapest,
Hungary

Andras Bittsanszky, Eszter Faki,
Éva Kinorányi, Orsolya Diófási-Kovács

Lentil lasagne

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Valencia,
Spain

Cristina Ruiz, Paloma Vicent,
Paola Hernandez, Hector Muelas,
Joachim Pomeu Mateus

Olla de la plana

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Nuoro,
Italy

Sara Porru, Stefano Floris

**Pumpkin risotto
with Parmigiano Reggiano fondue**

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Nuoro,
Italy

Sara Porru, Stefano Floris

Spelt and legume soup

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Viimsi,
Estonia

Kadi Bruus, Tina Saar

Tomato-lentil soup

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Dordogne,
France

Nicolas Lamastaes,
Vincent Demaison

**Winter galette with coral lentils,
sweet potato and spices**

54

Milan,
Italy

Chiara Mandelli, Cristina Sossan,
Diego Capocci, Elena Fucile

**Wholegrain fusilli with soy ragout
and Parmigiano Reggiano**

Autumn burger with coleslaw and potatoes

TYPE OF DISH

Burger

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Malmö, Sweden

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

A familiar and popular dish revisited with new ingredients. Before serving this dish, we will prepare a tasting of peas. The aim is to introduce new flavours and types of legumes. The peas used in this recipe are an ancient Swedish variety, which is not very common today.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

To show pupils that a vegetarian dish can be healthy and as good as a meat dish.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- LACTOSE FREE**
- Vegetarian
- Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	787	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	17	(% of total)
Fibre Content	20	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	8.4	(grams)
Saturated Fats	4.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Potatoes, raw	100	30	100	1.8	<0.1	1	-	88	-
Grey peas	70%	21	70	20.4	<0.1	6	0.7	220.5	-
Wheat bread roll, white hard	58%	17.4	58	2.8	0.4	3	0.3	160	-
Mushroom, raw	30%	9	30	1.5	<0.1	0.2	0.1	5.4	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	20%	6	20	-	-	-	14.9	180	-
Cabbage, green, raw	12%	3.6	12	4.1	<0.1	4.1	-	4.32	-
Sunflower seeds	10%	2	10	7.4	<0.1	-	6	64.7	-
Bread crumbs	8%	2.4	8	4.6	0.6	5.2	0.7	30.24	-
Leek, raw	8%	2.4	8	3	<0.1	3	-	2.24	-
Carrot, raw	4%	1.2	4	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	1.28	-
Mayonnaise	4%	1.2	4	0.2	0.3	3.4	8.5	26.56	-
Garlic, raw	2%	0.6	2	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	3.16	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Sautéed vegetables		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads and fillings
(2) Mayonnaise		Emulsion	To be used straight away	Can be used (almost) for everything
(3) Coleslaw salad		Chopping and mixing with mayo	To be used straight away	Tartare sauce, base for a pulses and cereals salad
(4) Roasted potatoes			4°C for up to 3 days	Potato salad, soups, fritters
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Boil the peas, (1) sauté the leek and garlic, add mushrooms in a pan (or bake in the oven). Mix the boiled and mashed peas with the roasted veggies, and breadcrumbs. Season and let the dough rest in the fridge. Once chilled, form the burger and pan fry them or bake them. For the (3) coleslaw salad, Make a (2) mayo sauce and mix it with finely chopped carrot and cabbage. Serve with coleslaw and (4) roasted potatoes.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 bowl of coleslaw 1 serving tray with burgers 1 serving tray with bread buns 1 serving tray with potatoes	320 gr per burger including potatoes and coleslaw.	Bread bun and potatoes to be served on the side. We want to introduce new vegetables in a familiar shape. The kids can construct their own burger as they prefer to eat it.

Lentil lasagne

TYPE OF DISH

Pasta & lasagne

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Budapest, Hungary

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

For all age groups: collecting folk traditions related to lentils.
For younger children: making pictures from lentils and other seeds using gluing techniques.
For elder students: seed germination experiment.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Lentils are an excellent source of protein and are part of traditional Hungarian cuisine, so children are familiar with them. As a hearty yet healthy alternative to traditional lasagna, lentil lasagna supports a balanced diet by offering a satisfying meal that is both nourishing and versatile.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
LACTOSE FREE
Vegetarian
Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	558	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	18	(% of total)
Fibre Content	11.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.5	(grams)
Sugars	14.2	(grams)
Saturated Fats	15.2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	9
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Milk, whole	100	7	70	-	<0.1	4.5	2.2	42.7	-
Pasta, egg, boiled	85.7%	6	60	2.2	<0.1	0.3	0.2	74.4	-
Tomato puree concentrated, tinned	85.7%	6	60	3.7	0.3	12.9	-	52.2	-
Carrot, raw	57.1%	4	40	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	12.8	10
Lentils, green / brown, dried	42.9%	3	30	18	<0.1	1	0.3	91.8	-
Cheese, Parmigiano Reggiano	42.9%	3	30	-	1	-	17.6	121.2	-
Celery, raw	28.6%	2	20	1.1	<0.1	1	-	2.8	10
Butter, unsalted	21.4%	1.5	15	-	<0.1	1.1	53.6	110.55	-
Flour wheat, wholemeal	21.4%	1.5	15	10.3	<0.1	5.4	0.3	49.5	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Vegetable base (soffritto)	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, vegetable stews or alongside starchy side dishes
	(2) Lentil ragout	Simmering	4°C for up to 3 days	Stand-alone ragu with a garnish, or with rice and pasta
	(3) Bechamellel sauce	Dry + wet cooking	4°C for up to 3 days	Can be used with other casseroles or to thicken any soups
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

For the **(1) vegetable base**, heat the oil in a pan, add the onion, carrot and celery, and gently cook for 20 mins until soft and brown. Add the garlic, cook for a few minutes, then stir in the lentils. Add the tomato sauce and spices. **(2) Simmer** for 20 mins, stirring occasionally the ragout. Meanwhile making **(3) bechamellel sauce**. Layer the pasta, lentil ragout and bechamellel. Sprinkle grated cheese on top and bake in the heated oven until crispy on the surface.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Baking trays	Serve squared in flat plate with fork. 350 gr per portion.	This is a favourite dish for children converted to a plant-based dish. This dish may be suitable for individuals looking for plant-based foods.

Olla de la plana

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Valencia, Spain

SEASON(S)
OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED
EDUCATIONAL
EXPERIENCE

By working in the school garden, learning about the the seasonality of vegetables and the introduction of legumes through progressive exposure. This educational project is called Growing Through Flavors.

KEYWORDS AND
COMMUNICATED
VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

This dish, Olla de la Plana, promotes the introduction of vegetables and legumes, encourages self-determined food choices and incorporates sustainable, plant-based ingredients. It also supports serving methods, as it can be offered in different textures (whole or pureed) and matches the visual appeal of green-coloured foods, reinforcing healthy and environment friendly eating habits.

INCLUSION
AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
Lactose Free
Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY:
NUTRITIONAL
PROFILE
PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	234	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	58	(% of total)
Fibre Content	12.3	(grams)
Sodium	0.8	(grams)
Sugars	7.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.8	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE:
ENVIRONMENTAL
AND SOCIAL
PROFILE

Main Ingredients	7
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Onions, raw	100	16.63	87.5	2.7	<0.1	4.5	0.1	32	5
Potatoes, raw	85.7%	14.25	75	1.8	<0.1	1	-	66	10
Beans, white, boiled	57.1%	9.50	50	9.9	<0.1	0.6	0.2	56.5	-
Carrot, raw	34.9%	5.8	30.5	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	10	10
Flat, green beans	28.6%	4.75	25	6.6	<0.1	0.6	0.5	30.5	1
Pumpkin, raw	28.6%	4.75	25	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	3.5	10
Chard	17.1%	2.85	15	2.5	0.2	3	-	4	-
Salt	2.9%	0.48	2.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Sweet paprika	2.9%	0.48	2.5	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	9	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	2.9%	0.48	2.5	-	-	-	14.9	22.5	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) White beans	Soaking + boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Spread, salads
	(2) Vegetable broth	Simmering	4°C for up to 3 days	Any stew, soup or even use it as boiling water for extra veggies
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Prepare a **(2) vegetable stock** with the skins and unused parts of the vegetables. Aside, rinse the **(1) white beans** from the water in which they have been soaking for 18 hours, and cook them in boiling water for around 1 hour (depending on the type of beans). Then in a frying pan, toast the spring onion and carrot in the olive oil, add the paprika and then the stock. Add the green beans to it, along with the pumpkin and the potato cut into 2 cm cubes and cook for 10 minutes over a medium heat. Thereafter, add the chopped swiss chard and cook over a low heat for a further 20 minutes, checking that all the ingredients are fully cooked. Season with salt. It can be served as it is or pureed and made into a fine cream.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
One single tray. It can be served in the self-service or buffet line of the dining room.	As it is a hot dish: keep it warm for consumption, served in a deep dish with a spoon. Serve at a temperature above 65°C. 300 ml per portion.	Good for the planet: uses local, seasonal, and plant-based ingredients, reducing waste and supporting the environment. Nourishing and energizing: packed with vegetables, legumes, and fiber for a healthy and balanced meal. Rooted in tradition: a classic dish from the Region of Valencia, enjoyed for generations.

Pumpkin risotto with Parmigiano Reggiano fondue

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Nuoro, Italy

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

An educational workshop dedicated to pumpkin and vegetables in general will be held both in the classroom and at the farm. This will allow children to discover the cultivation of pumpkins and their seasonality. By getting to know them up close and tasting delicious related recipes, the workshop aims to promote the consumption of these healthy ingredients.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

This dish aligns perfectly with the aim of creating a balanced and delicious meal. The umami of the aged cheese, combined with the roasted sweetness of the pumpkin and the aromatic herbs, creates a harmonious flavor profile that appeals to children while being nutritionally balanced. This dish supports plant-based proteins, it is colorful, and promotes healthy eating habits.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	209	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	26	(% of total)
Fibre Content	1	(grams)
Sodium	0.1	(grams)
Sugars	0.8	(grams)
Saturated Fats	3.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Rice, white, raw	100	25.50	30	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	105.6	8
Pumpkin, raw	66.7%	17	20	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	2.8	-
Cheese, Parmigiano Reggiano	50%	12.75	15	-	1	-	17.6	60.6	-
Milk, whole	33.3%	8.5	10	-	<0.1	4.5	2.2	6	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	10%	2.55	3	-	-	-	14.9	27	-
Pepper, black/white	3.3%	0.85	1	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	3.32	-
Rosemary, dried	3.3%	3.3	1	17.6	<0.1	-	0.7	3.74	-
Salt	0.2%	<0.1	0.05	-	33.8	-	-	-	0.1

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Cooked rice		Steaming	4°C for up to 2 days	Salads, fillings, fritters, soups
(2) Pumpkin purée		Roasting + seasoning + blending	4°C for up to 2 days	Pasta with pumpkin, Chickpea and pumpkin meatballs
(3) Cheese Fondue		Melting and mixing	4°C for up to 2 days	Pasta with parmesan fondue
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Season pumpkin skin on with extra virgin olive oil, salt and rosemary in the oven. Blend it and seasonin it obtaining a **(1) pumpkin purée**. Steam the **(2) carnaroli rice** and add the pumpkin cream. Prepare a **(3) cheese fondue** with milk and grated parmigiano reggiano. Add the fondue to the risotto and serve.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Large pot with pumpkin risotto. Pot with cheese fondue.	50-60 grams of risotto and 3-5 grams of fondue for kindergarten. 60-80 grams of risotto and 5 grams of fondue for primary school.	Cold-weather vegetarian dish prepared with autumn veggies.

Spelt and legume soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Nuoro, Italy

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Ci.Buo

This is an idea of the SF4C working group, who proposed 10 different thematic workshops to promote awareness among pupils and educators on healthy, sustainable and tasty meals. Educational workshops were held in schools, one of these was related to the topic of legumes and to this recipe too.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

The spelt and legume soup embodies the principles of a systemic and agroecological approach by incorporating nutritious, cyclically sourced ingredients. Promote sustainability, food waste reduction, and holistic health, aligning with the progressive exposure and relational food practices.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	414	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	32	(% of total)
Fibre Content	10	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	4.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.5	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Semi-wholemeal spelt	100	21.25	25	-	-	-	-	335	30
Carrot, raw	80%	17	20	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	6.4	20
Tomatoes, tinned	40%	8.5	10	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	2.4	10
Lentils green / brown, dried	20%	4.25	5	18	<0.1	1	0.3	15.3	8
Beans white / brown, dried	20%	4.25	5	18.1	<0.1	3.4	0.4	15.7	8
Chickpeas, boiled	20%	4.25	5	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	6.9	8
Celery, raw	12%	2.55	3	1.1	<0.1	1	-	0.42	5
Onion red, raw	12%	2.55	3	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	1.10	5
Oil, olive, extra virgin	12%	2.55	3	-	-	-	14.9	27	5
Rosemary, dried	4%	0.85	1	17.6	<0.1	-	0.7	3.74	1
Salt	0.2%	0.04	0.05	-	33.8	-	-	-	0.1

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Soffritto		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Stews, soups, dips
(2) Lentils, beans, chickpeas		Soaking + boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Burgers and salad
(3) Semi-wholemeal spelt		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Spelt salad with vegetables, every rice dice
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Sauté celery, carrots and onions until light brown ((1) **soffritto**). Add the tomato sauce and the legumes, previously (2) **soaked** in water for at least 8 hours. Add the water and seasoning and bring it to a (2) **boil**. Lower the heat and cook for 3 hours. The last 30 minutes add the (3) **spelt**, season with salt and finish cooking. Add a touch of raw oil at the end.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
One-pot meal	350 g per portion.	This vegetarian main course featuring spelt and legumes, provides a rich source of plant-based proteins and fibers.

Tomato-lentil soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Viimsi, Estonia

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

A soup of joy!

The workshop focuses on simple and healthy food preparation, teaching pupils to use wholesome ingredients such as lentils and tomatoes. In addition, they will learn how to reduce the use of salt and sugar and emphasize flavors with natural and healthy seasoning techniques. The workshop will also discuss the benefits of food products and participants will be able to test various flavoring techniques in practice.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

This recipe combines nutritional value, taste and care, supporting the well-being of school children. It also expresses love and attention to detail, offering a taste that brings joy and brings people together. Cooking is not only a practical activity, but an outlet through which healing and uplifting moments can be created.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	159	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	20	(% of total)
Fibre Content	7.5	(grams)
Sodium	0.6	(grams)
Sugars	4.1	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Vegetable stock	100	0.60	170	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	10.2	-
Tomatoes, tinned	21.8%	0.13	37	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	8.88	2
Lentils green / brown, dried	17.1%	0.10	29	18	<0.1	1	0.3	88.7	-
Carrot, raw	12.9%	<0.1	22	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	7	20
Leek, raw	8.8%	<0.1	15	3	<0.1	3	-	4.2	24
Onion, red, raw	5.3%	<0.1	9	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	3.33	16
Basil, fresh	3.5%	<0.1	6	3.9	<0.1	5.1	0.2	2.88	16
Parsley, fresh	3.5%	<0.1	6	5	<0.1	-	0.1	2.22	26
Garlic, raw	1.8%	<0.1	3	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	4.74	22
Oil, olive, extra virgin	1.8%	<0.1	3	-	-	-	14.9	27	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Aromatic base	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days or freezing	Soups, stews and sauces
	(2) Soup	Simmering	4°C for up to 3 days	Ragout
	(3) Leek	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Autumn salad
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Prepare an **(1) aromatic base**, roasting chopped carrot, onion and garlic on medium heat with olive oil, then add the vegan stock and bring to a boil. Add the washed lentils, the tomato sauce and season with herbs. Keep on simmering until the **(2) soup** done. Check the taste and add seasonings if necessary. Serve with gently roasted **(3) leeks**, dried onion crisps and, optional, beetroot powder. During the tests, the children can choose what to decorate their soup with.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 pot of soup 1 tray of leek	350 gr per portion.	Children can choose their own soup decorations to create a playful interest in healthy foods. The classes eat in groups with the teachers and later in the classroom can give a sensory evaluation of the food.

Winter galette with coral lentils, sweet potato and spices

TYPE OF DISH

Patties & galettes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Dordogne, France

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Exploring spices & flavors

Tasting and discussion to discover the origins and uses of spices like paprika, curry and cumin, and olive oil, to naturally enhance flavors. Learning how spices can reduce the need for salt and sugar while making meals more delicious.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Introducing students to the richness of plant-based cuisine and the role of spices in enhancing flavor without excess salt. It's a comforting, nutritious, and delicious way to enjoy legumes.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	398	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	18	(% of total)
Fibre Content	14.5	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	5.6	(grams)
Saturated Fats	4.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	9
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Potato, sweet, raw	100	0.60	60	2.4	<0.1	5.5	0.1	54.6	-
Lentils, red, dried	50%	0.30	30	18	<0.1	1	0.3	91.8	-
Carrot, raw	33.3%	0.20	20	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	6.4	-
Cheese, Emmenthaler	25%	0.15	15	-	0.4	-	19.5	58.05	-
Egg, whole chicken, raw	20%	0.12	12	-	0.2	0.2	3.1	15.84	-
Onion, red, raw	16.7%	0.10	10	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	3.7	-
Flour, wheat, wholemeal	16.7%	0.10	10	10.3	<0.1	5.4	0.3	33	-
Cumin seed, dried	16.7%	0.10	10	10.3	0.2	-	1.9	42.7	-
Linseeds	16.7%	0.10	10	34.8	<0.1	-	2.9	47.7	-
Paprika powder	8.3%	<0.1	5	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	17.95	-
Garlic, raw	6.7%	<0.1	4	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	6.32	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3.3%	<0.1	2	-	-	-	14.9	18	-
Salt	0.8%	<0.1	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	0.8%	<0.1	0.5	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	1.66	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Coral lentils		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, pasta dishes, salads
(2) Sweet potato purée		Baking/steaming + mashing	4°C for up to 3 days	Potato pudding and desserts, side dishes, soups
(3) Galette raw mixture		Mixing and shaping	4°C for up to 3 days	Pitas or burgers, salads
(4) Finished galettes		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Burgers and soups
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Rinse the (1) coral lentils and cook them in boiling salted water for about 10 minutes (they should be tender but not mushy). Drain them well and let them cool. Cook the (2) sweet potatoes (either in the oven or by steaming), then mash them into a purée. Store the peels for future preparations (i.e. making crisps). Grate the carrots, chop the onion, and finely slice the garlic. For the (3) galette raw mixture, in a large mixing bowl, combine the coral lentils, sweet potato purée, grated carrots, onion, garlic, grated cheese, eggs, and spices. Add flour or breadcrumbs to thicken the mixture - it should be firm enough to shape into galettes. Adjust the seasoning with salt and pepper. Take a small portion of the mixture in your hands and form galettes about 8-10 cm in diameter. Preheat the oven to 180°C, bake the galettes on a baking sheet lined with parchment paper for 20-30 minutes. These (4) finished galettes can be prepared in advance and reheated in the oven before serving. They can be frozen after cooking for later use.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Serve the galettes with a winter salad (red cabbage, corn salad, apples, walnuts) and a lemon yogurt sauce or Tahini sauce.	190 gr per person on a flat plate.	Serve with a big smile!
For a snack version, place the galettes in pita bread or a burger bun with grilled vegetables and homemade tomato sauce.		

Wholegrain fusilli with soy ragout and Parmigiano Reggiano

TYPE OF DISH

Pasta & lasagne

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Milan, Italy

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Presenting the daily recipe through posters located into the school canteen, or carrying out a workshop made by food policy officers of the Municipality.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

- High fibre content
- Excellent substitute for meat (soy in granular form)
- Traditional Italian dish
- Progressive exposure

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- VEGETARIAN**
- Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	378	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	8	(% of total)
Fibre Content	8.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	6.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.8	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	9
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Pasta, wholemeal, raw	100	140	70	6.9	<0.1	3.5	0.3	243.6	-
Tomatoes, tinned	100%	140	70	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	16.8	-
Minced meat, vegetarian, based on soya	50%	70	35	8.9	0.5	2	0.2	51.8	-
Carrot, raw	10%	14	7	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	2.24	-
Onion, red	7.1%	10	5	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	1.85	-
Celery, raw	7.1%	10	5	1.1	<0.1	1	-	0.7	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	7.1%	10	5	-	-	-	14.9	45	-
Cheese, Parmigiano Reggiano	5.7%	8	4	-	1	-	17.6	16.16	-
Salt	0.4%	0.6	0.3	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Celery		Browning of vegetables as a base for the tomatoe souce	The product can be kept in cold or refrigerated line for 3/4 days.	The soya ragout can also be served as a side dish of the polenta/ smashed potatoes.
(2) Onion		Browning of vegetables as a base for the tomatoe souce	The various components of the dish are prepared and delivered on the tables in max 3 hours.	
(3) Carrot		Browning of vegetables as a base for the tomatoe souce		
(4) Granular soy		Rehydrating of the soy granulate in water		
(5) Tomato sauce		Mixing with tomato sauce		

DIRECTIONS

For the ragout, soak the soybeans in cold water 30 mins before the use. Aside in a pan toast **(1, 2, 3) celery, carrot and onion** with olive oil until soft and gently brown, then add the tomato pulp and salt. Let the **(5) sauce** simmer until round and umami, then blend it. Add the previously **(4) drained soya** and let it cook, adding water if necessary. Cook the whole grain fusilli in salted water, drain them "al dente". Drizzle the pasta with the remaining oil. Pair pasta with the ragout and sprinkle Parmigiano Reggiano on top to taste.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
The pasta and the sauce has to be combined just before serving and the parmesan cheese is added at the top if the children ask for it.	In order to fulfill the expected quantity per kid, the amount of grams per portion has to be communicated to the person in charge of the service.	This dish is a revised version of the very traditional ragout pasta well-known all over Italy.
	340 gr per portion.	

GOOD

GASTRONOMIC
CULTURE

TEXTURE

ACCEP
TABILITY

TASTE

CONSTRUCTION

PALATABILITY

Balanced dishes

When designing recipes for school canteens, it is therefore essential not only to take into account the pleasure and positive emotions that pupils should experience, but also to include foods that are good for them and essential for the body. In this context, school meals, which for many individuals may be the main meal of the day, play a crucial role in ensuring a balanced intake of essential nutrients.

Designing a balanced meal today means providing a complete and good quality profile of macronutrients, together with a wide variety of micronutrients (such as essential minerals and vitamins) found mainly in plant-based ingredients.

The recipes collected in this chapter are practical and applicable examples of how to provide a complete and balanced nutritional intake, paying attention to both the quantity and quality of the nutrients involved.

There are three main strategies behind the creation of these recipes:

- recipes designed from scratch to prevent nutrient waste caused by food scraps, as in the case of **Potatoes, tomato and coral lentils and crunchy vegetables** or **Autumn ragout with rice and vegetables**;
- adapting or taking inspiration from other gastronomic cultures, as in the case of **PPP. Plant-Protein Power Curry** or even **Persian Stew with roasted potatoes and seasonal vegetables**, presented here in a vegetarian version;
- offering local recipes that promote traditional diets as a contemporary model, as in the case of the traditional **Empedrao rice with vegetables and Romesco sauce**: a rice dish combined here with the famous **Romesco sauce** for an extra boost of good fats.

You can explore these topics further by consulting the *Progressive Display and Circular Cuisine* chapter of the *School Menu Design Handbook*, particularly pages 80↔85.

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Leuven,
Belgium

Ellen Vantomme, Sarah Bruinaars,
Sofie Verhoeven, Dimitri Tytgat

Asian style vegetables and lentil stir fry

68

Ghent,
Belgium

Vincent Demaison,
Nicolas Lamastaes

Autumn ragout with rice and vegetables

72

Czech
Republic

Cristina Ruiz, Paloma Vicent,
Paola Hernandez, Hector Muelas,
Joachim Pomeu Mateus

Carrot burger

76

Valencia,
Spain

Andrea Hruskova, Dagmar Sedlářová,
Tom Václavík

**Empedrao rice with vegetables
and Romesco sauce**

62

80

Leuven,
Belgium

Ellen Vandenbroucke, Marlieke Bender,
Marieke Vangoidsenhoven,
Tom Berghmans, Benoît Reisner

**Persian Stew with roasted potatoes
and seasonal vegetables**

63

84

Dordogne,
France

Ellen Vandenbroucke, Marlieke Bender,
Marieke Vangoidsenhoven,
Tom Berghmans, Benoît Reisner

**Potatoes, tomato, coral lentils
and crunchy vegetables**

88

Nürnberg
and Essen,
Germany

Alice Baumgärtner, Manuel Poschadel,
Christian Sandner, Stephanie Schielein,
Karin Schmidt, Vera Stöbel

**PPP.
Plant-Protein Power Curry**

Asian style vegetables and lentil stir fry

TYPE OF DISH

Vegetables & legumes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Leuven, Belgium

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

Spring

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Learning about legumes

A workshop about recognizing the different varieties of pulses and the beneficial features related. Putting the hands on, making the dough for lentils and broccoli fritters (or whatever is leftover from the prep of this recipe).

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Processing of a varied mix of nutrients in a complete and balanced dish.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	607	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	40	(% of total)
Fibre Content	18.5	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	3.1	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Lentils, green/brown, dried	100	4	80	18	<0.1	1	0.3	244.8	-
Rice, basmati	100	4	80	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	281.6	-
Carrot, raw	62.5%	2.5	50	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	16	3
Broccoli, boiled	62.5%	2.5	50	2.7	<0.1	-	0.1	13.5	20
Ginger, root	6.3%	0.25	5	2	<0.1	1.7	0.2	4.05	2
Garlic, raw	6.3%	0.25	5	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	7.9	2
Soy, sauce	6.3%	0.25	5	0.1	4.8	0.6	-	2	-
Cilantro	6.3%	0.25	5	-	-	-	-	0.01	-
Oil, sesame	2.5%	0.1	2	-	<0.1	-	14.5	17.96	-
Oil, sunflower seed	2.5%	0.1	2	-	-	-	10.6	17.94	-
Paprika, powder	0.6%	<0.1	0.5	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	1.795	4

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Asian style base	Sautering	4°C or room temp if pasteurized	Indian curry, salads, miso soup
	(2) Broccoli	Boiling	4°C for up to 2 days	Soup, salads
	(3) Carrots and paprika	Roasting	4°C for up to 2 days	Velloute
	(4) Lentils	Boiling	4°C for up to 2 days	Dahl, lentil fritters, hummus
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Cut **(2) broccoli** into small flowers and scald for about 3 minutes and drain.
(3) Peel carrots and slice them, then bake them lightly in the oven (al dente) adding paprika.
(4) Boil lentils and drain. Sauté the onions, ginger and garlic in oil, then add Soy, sauce and sesame oil (**(1) asian style base**). Gently simmer and finally add broccoli, carrots, paprika and lentils together with the finely chopped cilantro. Cook and drain the rice.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of boiled rice 1 tray with the stir fry mix	Keep warm in bain-marie. 90 grams of rice. 220 grams of stirfry mix.	This dish is also modular because it can be served in such a way to let the kids express their own self-determined choices on i.e. the topping to pair to it.

Autumn ragout with rice and vegetables

TYPE OF DISH

Stew & ragout

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Ghent, Belgium

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Guessing game

Showcase different sorts of legumes in the school canteen and children can guess which ones are in the dish they are eating.

Field trip

Children can visit different production of the ingredients used in the dish and do interviews to the farmers.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Adaptation of a veal ragout with pasta. The same mediterranean feel, but with whole grain rice, roasted autumn veg and legumes in a fragrant tomato sauce.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	252	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	47	(% of total)
Fibre Content	14.8	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	1.6	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (Kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Rice, brown, raw	100	6	60	3	<0.1	1	0.6	214.2	N/D
Soya, beans, boiled	2.9%	0.18	60	6.5	<0.1	-	0.8	73.8	N/D
Chickpeas, boiled	2.9%	0.18	60	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	82.8	N/D
Celeriac, raw	66.7%	4	40	4.9	<0.1	-	-	15.2	N/D
Peas, raw	66.7%	4	40	4.7	<0.1	1	-	26	N/D
Cabbage, savoy	66.7%	4	40	2.5	<0.1	-	-	6.8	N/D
Mushroom, raw	1%	<0.1	20	1.5	<0.1	0.2	0.1	3.6	N/D
Tomatoes, classic, round, raw	0.7%	<0.1	15	1.3	<0.1	2.9	0.1	3	N/D
Shallot	25%	1.50	15	-	-	-	-	-	N/D
Onion, red, raw	16.7%	1	10	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	3.7	N/D
Oil, rosemary	0.1%	<0.1	2	-	-	-	14.9	18	N/D
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3.3%	0.2	2	-	-	-	14.9	18	N/D
Garlic, raw	-	<0.1	0.5	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	0.79	N/D
Garlic	0.8%	<0.1	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	N/D

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Ragout		Braising (wet cooking + dry cooking) or pasteurising	Dry storage	Vegetarian chili, tagliatelle with vegetarian ragout
(2) Whole grain rice		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Cold as a component in a rice salad, or in a wrap with vegetables
(3) Autumn vegetables		Roasting	4°C for up to 2 days	As a an extra warm vegetable side to another dish
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Cook the (2) whole grain rice in boiling salted water, or steam it in oven (optional, add shallot and spices).

(1) Ragout: soak the chickpeas overnight. Cook until tender. Cook the mushrooms briefly in water with a drizzle of lemon juice. For the sauce, fry garlic in olive oil until fragrant. Then add tomato paste, tomato cubes, spices and Oil, rosemary to it. Let simmer for a half an hour. Add fresh soybeans, then cooked chickpeas and cooked mushrooms. Let it cook for another 10 minutes. Season to taste.

(3) Vegetables: cook the thinly sliced cabbage in salted water. Do the same with the celery and the peas. Gently mix the vegetables together. Season with olive oil and spices.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 big pot of ragout 1 tray of boiled rice 1 tray of vegetables	Ragout: 160 gr Whole grain rice: 150 gr Autumn vegetables: 130 gr	Encourage kids to mix the rice with the ragout. It makes the rice nice and juicy.

Carrot burger

TYPE OF DISH

Burger

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Czech Republic

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Burger puzzle

A veggie burger can taste great even more if diy.

Class activity: letting the kids design menus including the five colors of health.

Canteen activity: children can choose different types of vegetables and legumes to make a burger. Perceiving and trying different tastes, colors and smells.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Processing of seasonal vegetables. Creating a collage of vegetables that are in season in spring. It is a complete meal containing a complete nutrients profile.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	806	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	44	(% of total)
Fibre Content	16	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	12	(grams)
Saturated Fats	5.5	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Carrot, raw	100	1.2	120	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	38.4	N/D
Potatoes, raw	83.3%	1	100	1.8	<0.1	1	-	88	N/D
Tofu, smoked	58.3%	0.7	70	2	<0.1	0.5	0.8	83.3	N/D
Onion, red, raw	41.7%	0.5	50	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	18.5	N/D
Lettuce, romaine, raw	25%	0.3	30	2.1	<0.1	1.2	-	5.1	N/D
Radish, raw	25%	0.3	30	0.9	<0.1	3	-	6.6	N/D
Oatmeal	25%	0.3	30	7.3	<0.1	2	1.3	111.9	N/D
Millet, raw	23.3%	0.28	28	3	<0.1	-	0.8	103.6	N/D
Lentils, red	16.7%	0.2	20	18	<0.1	1	0.3	61.2	N/D
Cashew nuts, unsalted	16.7%	0.2	20	3.8	<0.1	5	8.4	123	N/D
Oil, olive, extra virgin	12.5%	0.15	15	-	-	-	14.9	135	N/D
Spices	3.3%	<0.1	4	-	-	-	-	-	N/D
Oil, rapeseed	2.5%	<0.1	3	-	-	-	6.9	26.97	N/D
Lemon, juice, fresh	1.7%	<0.1	2	0.3	<0.1	2	-	0.94	N/D
Mustard	1.7%	<0.1	2	3	1.4	2.7	0.4	2.58	N/D
Garlic, raw	0.4%	<0.1	0.5	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	0.79	N/D
Vinegar	0.4%	<0.1	0.5	-	<0.1	0.6	-	0.11	N/D
Salt	0.4%	<0.1	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	N/D

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Burger dough	Boiling + roasting + mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, vegetarian loaf
	(2) Mashed potatoes and millet	Boiling + mashing	4°C for up to 3 days	Can be used instead of traditional rice in dishes to promote versatility
	(3) Cashew dip	Soaking + mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Can be used paired with roasted vegetables
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS	
	For the (1) carrot burger , sauté carrots and onions, add grated tofu and boiled red lentils. Pour in oatmeal, add spices and prepare the dough, let it ticken in the fridge and then form meatballs. Brush with oil and bake at 180°C for 20 minutes.
	(2) Mash boiled potatoes with boiled millet and sauteed onion.
	For the (3) dip , soak the cashew in double the amount of water for two hours, then strain it and add garlic, olive oil, lemon juice, apple cider vinegar, mustard, salt and mix everything until smooth. Mix the leafy salad with chopped radish and season with olive oil, salt and vinegar.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of burgers 1 tray of mashed potatoes 1 tray of salad 1 bowl of dip Serving temperature: Warm Serving tools: Flat plates and a fork and knife	Service: Serve immediately after preparation for the best flavor and texture. Holding: The dish can be kept warm in oven. Portion weight: 500 gr.	This dish is ideal for vegetarian or vegan menus and caters well to individuals seeking plant-based meals.

Empedrao rice with vegetables and Romesco sauce

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Valencia, Spain

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

We are developing an educational project called Growing Through Flavors in which the school garden plays a key role in our vision of the school dining experience. For the summer version of this recipe, we conduct workshops where each student adapts and creates their own salad using fresh and seasonal ingredients.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

This dish embodies everything we stand for in SchoolFood4Change: it is flavorful, healthy, made with locally sourced ingredients, rooted in tradition, and most importantly, it represents the Spanish culinary heritage. Moreover, the versatility and adaptability of this dish makes it perfect for cooking at any time of the year.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	748	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	37	(% of total)
Fibre Content	15.6	(grams)
Sodium	1.7	(grams)
Sugars	6.7	(grams)
Saturated Fats	4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Rice. white. raw	100	14.25	75	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	264	-
Beans white/ brown dried	66.7%	9.5	50	18.1	<0.1	3.4	0.4	157	-
Leek. raw	50%	7.13	37.5	3	<0.1	3	-	10.5	5
Pumpkin. raw	33.3%	4.75	25	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	3.5	10
Tomatoes. tinned	33.3%	4.75	25	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	6	5
Carrot. raw	33.3%	4.75	25	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	8	-
Oil. olive. extra virgin	26.7%	3.8	20	-	-	-	14.9	180	-
Beans. French. raw	23.3%	3.33	17.5	3.6	<0.1	1.2	0.1	4.37	5
Bread. wheat. rye. wholemeal	20%	2.85	15	0.90	0.4	2.3	0.4	35.1	-
Pepper. sweet. red. raw	16.7%	2.38	12.5	0.23	<0.1	4.3	-	3.12	20
Hazelnuts. unsalted	13.3%	1.9	10	0.82	<0.1	4.3	4.6	67	-
Salt	6.7%	0.95	5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Paprika. powder	3.3%	0.48	2.5	0.50	<0.1	-	1.7	8.97	-
Garlic. raw	0.3%	<0.1	0.25	-	<0.1	1	0.1	<0.1	5

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/ Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Beans		Soak 24/48 h and then boil	In the summer version, preparation is done the day before.	Salad version for summer.
(2) Low refined rice		Boiling	Store the semifinished products in a Tupper or other airtight container in the fridge and label with the date of preparation and expiry date (3 days).	In autumn and winter, it's thicker or soupier, served as a spoon dish. And in spring, its dry version in Paella.
(3) Washed, peeled, and chopped vegetables		Sauté		
(4) Vegetable broth		Boil the peels and vegetable scraps in a saucepan		
(5) Romesco sauce		Toast and blend all the ingredients		

DIRECTIONS

For the **(5) Romesco sauce**, toast stale whole wheat bread, red bell pepper, tomato and hazelnut in oven until they brown, then put them in a blender, add extra virgin olive oil, salt (and few drops of vinegar) and blend until you get a thick puree. For the **(2) rice**, prepare a **(4) vegetable broth** with the peels and vegetable scraps and set aside. In a paella pan, **(3) sauté** the spring onion, carrot, pumpkin and green beans cut into 1 cm cubes in olive oil. Add the chopped garlic, paprika and tomato and cook until the water evaporates. Add the rice and stir until it becomes translucent. Moisten with the vegetable broth and adjust the salt. Add the saffron infusion (optional). After 10 minutes of cooking, add the boiled beans and finish on a low heat. At the end, pipe small dots of Romesco sauce on the dish.

Notes:

- This dish can be served year-round by incorporating seasonal vegetables and using different techniques to finish the rice.
- It can range from salads in warm weather to thicker or soupier versions for colder days.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Depending on the season, use a low saucepan, shallow casserole, paella pan, or oven tray.	Depending on the season, it can be served on a flat plate with a fork or in a deep dish with a spoon. Serve 220 g per portion.	Full use of raw materials and reuse of stale bread for the preparation of the Romesco sauce.

Persian Stew with seasonal vegetables

TYPE OF DISH

Stew & ragout

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Leuven, Belgium

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Month by month

For each dish we present we can talk about the seasonal vegetables and the children experience how the dish changes each few months. It is also easy to cook together and legumes can be gradually introduced.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

We combine some traditional ingredients with the seasonal vegetable (adaptable to each season). We use chickpeas, soy beans and nuts as a protein source but they can be progressively introduced instead of the original recipe with chicken.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	514	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	41	(% of total)
Fibre Content	12.7	(grams)
Sodium	0.6	(grams)
Sugars	17.4	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Chickpeas, raw	100	6	60	-	-	-	-	-	N/D
Bread, wheat, white, pita	100	6	60	2.1	0.4	2.4	0.2	147	N/D
Stock vegetable	91.7%	5.5	55	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	3.3	N/D
Celeriac, raw	66.7%	4	40	4.9	<0.1	-	-	15.2	N/D
Cabbage, green, raw	66.7%	4	40	4.1	<0.1	4.1	-	14.4	N/D
Pumpkin, raw	66.7%	4	40	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	5.6	N/D
Carrot, raw	33.3%	2	20	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	6.4	N/D
Potatoes, raw	33.3%	2	20	1.8	<0.1	1	-	17.6	N/D
Apricots, dried	33.3%	2	20	14.4	<0.1	56	-	57	N/D
Almonds, skin, unsalted	33.3%	2	20	10.2	<0.1	4.4	3.6	124.4	N/D
Soya, beans, boiled	33.3%	2	20	6.5	<0.1	-	0.8	24.6	N/D
Oil, olive, extra virgin	16.7%	1	10	-	-	-	14.9	90	N/D
Onion, red, raw	11.7%	0.7	7	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	2.6	N/D
Coriander	4.2%	0.25	2.5	-	-	-	-	<0.1	N/D
Tahin	1.5%	<0.1	0.9	12.4	0.4	1.6	7.6	5.26	N/D
Ras el hanout	1.5%	<0.1	0.9	-	-	-	-	-	N/D
Garlic, raw	1.2%	<0.1	0.7	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	1.10	N/D
Salt	0.8%	<0.1	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	N/D
Lemon, juice, fresh	0.5%	<0.1	0.3	0.3	<0.1	2	-	0.14	N/D
Cumin, seed, dried	0.3%	<0.1	0.15	10.5	0.2	-	1.9	0.64	N/D

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Persian stew base	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Base for other stews or soups
	(2) Seasonal vegetables	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Base for curry, mix with pasta, serve as a side
	(3) Hummus	Blending	4°C for up to 3 days	Added to mashed potatoes or soups
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS	
	<p>For the (1) stew base, peel, cut and slice onion and garlic. Mix together with previously boiled yellow split peas, cut potatoes, dried apricots and almonds, season with ras el hanout and toast in the oven at 180°C. Move everything to a large pot, add the vegetable stock and let it simmer for at least 30 minutes. Clean and cut the (2) seasonal vegetables in the desired shape, season with salt, turmeric and oil. Roast in the oven for 45 minutes. Once cooked, you can choose to add the roasted vegetables to the stew base or to leave them aside.</p> <p>For the (3) hummus: boil in water soaked yellow split peas, locally grown in our region, add lemon juice, tahini, cumin, salt and pepper and blend.</p> <p>Serve the stew on the bottom and then top of with the roasted vegetables. We sprinkle the almonds and coriander. Bread and humus can be served separately or shared at the table.</p>

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 pot of persian stew 1 tray of roasted vegetables 1 bowl of hummus 1 tray of flat bread	Bowl or plate. It is also possible to leave the persian stew and roasted vegetables separate so children can more easily choose and portion.	The vegetables can be changed according to the season. Chicken or veal in the traditional recipe can be gradually replaced by legumes.

Potatoes, tomato, coral lentils and crunchy vegetables

TYPE OF DISH

Vegetables & legumes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Dordogne, France

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Cuisine & Discovery

Organizing cooking workshops to help children to explore different ingredients. Inviting local organic producers during meal service to promote communication, confidence and awareness on sustainable food sourcing.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Encourage students to eat more vegetables and showcase how varied, delicious and appealing they are.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	422	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	69	(% of total)
Fibre Content	16.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	12.1	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	9
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Courgettes, raw	100	1	100	0.9	<0.1	2.3	0.01	18	-
Potatoes, raw	90%	0.9	90	1.8	<0.1	1	-	79.2	11 (upcycling)
Tomatoes, classic, round, raw	90%	0.9	90	1.3	<0.1	2.9	0.01	18	11
Carrot, raw	62.5%	0.63	62.5	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.01	20	12
Lentils, red, dried	50%	0.5	50	18	<0.1	1	0.3	153	-
Pepper, sweet, red, raw	32%	0.32	32	1.8	<0.1	4.3	-	8	-
Onion, red, raw	20%	0.2	20	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	7.4	10
Basil, beans, French, raw	15%	0.15	15	3.6	<0.1	1.2	0.1	3.75	33
Garlic, raw	10%	0.1	10	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	15.8	20
Basil, fresh	10%	0.1	10	3.9	<0.1	5.1	0.2	4.8	20
Oil, olive, extra virgin	10%	0.1	10	-	-	-	14.9	90	-
Oregano, dried	1%	<0.1	1	15	<0.1	-	2.1	3.6	-
Salt	0.5%	<0.1	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	0.1%	-	0.05	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	0.16	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Baked potatoes		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Potato pudding
(2) Tomato and coral lentil compote		Wet cooking + mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, pasta dishes, salads
(3) Crunchy vegetables		Wet + dry cooking	4°C for up to 3 days	Cous cous or rice salads
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

For the **(1) baked potatoes**, season the potatoes with salt and pepper and bake them for 1 hour at 150°C. Store the peels for future preparations (i.e. making crisps).

For the **(2) tomato and coral lentil compote**, peel and slice onions and garlic.

Then toast them in olive oil over medium heat. Add the chopped peeled tomatoes, season with salt and pepper and simmer over low heat for about 30 minutes. After that, add the lentils to the tomato compote and cook for around 12 minutes. Mix the lentils into the tomato compote and add fresh basil leaves just before serving.

For the **(3) crunchy vegetables**, peel and cut carrots, zucchini, bell peppers and green beans and cut them into stripes or sticks.

Blanch the green beans in boiling salted water for 5 minutes to save the shining green color, then drain. Quickly sauté the vegetables in olive oil over high heat to keep them crispy.

Season with salt and pepper.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of mixed vegetables	Serve in a flat plate.	Serve with a big smile!
1 tray of lentil-tomato compote		
1 tray of baked potatoes	200 gr per serving.	

PPP. Plant-Protein Power Curry

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Nürnberg and Essen, Germany

SEASON(S)
OF THE DISH

Autumn

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED
EDUCATIONAL
EXPERIENCE

In certain cases taste develops over time. Let's have a blind-tasting (no yucky stuff, I promise) Prep makes cooking so much easier. Let's learn what to prep in advance and what to cook later, or à la minute as people french say.

KEYWORDS AND
COMMUNICATED
VALUES

*>why I am preparing
this dish*

This dish can be prepared in every season, using different veggies. In a typical indian Curry the veggies are hot but still crunchy, which makes them keep nutritional value

INCLUSION
AND ALLERGENS

*> for whom I am
preparing this dish*

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY:
NUTRITIONAL
PROFILE
PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	429	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	21	(% of total)
Fibre Content	6.5	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	5.2	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE:
ENVIRONMENTAL
AND SOCIAL
PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion (gr)					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Rice, basmati	100	5.94	90	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	316.8	-
Tomatoes, tinned	58.9%	3.5	53	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	12.72	-
Chickpeas, boiled	33.3%	1.98	30	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	41.4	-
Onion, red, raw	22.2%	1.32	20	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	7.4	20
Tofu, smoked	22.2%	1.32	20	2	<0.1	0.5	0.8	23.8	-
Carrot, raw	16.7%	0.99	15	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	4.8	25
Parsnip, raw	16.7%	0.99	15	4.7	<0.1	5.4	0.2	10.65	25
Garlic, raw	1.1%	<0.1	1	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	1.58	-
Soy, sauce	1.1%	<0.1	1	0.1	4.8	0.6	-	0.4	-
Syrup, rice, malt	1.1%	<0.1	1	-	<0.1	44.5	-	2.92	-
Lemon, juice, fresh	1.1%	<0.1	1	0.3	<0.1	2	-	0.47	-
Coriander	0.6%	<0.1	0.5	-	-	-	-	<0.1	-
Anise, seed	0.6%	<0.1	0.5	14.6	<0.1	31.5	0.6	1.92	-
Cumin, seed, dried	0.6%	<0.1	0.5	10.5	0.2	-	1.9	2.13	-
Paprika, powder	0.6%	<0.1	0.5	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	1.79	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Curry Sauce	Simmering + blending	4°C for up to 3 days	A vast amount of curries
	(2) Rooted vegetables	Steaming	4°C for up to 3 days	Roasted, cooked, steamed
	(3) Coriander-Chutney	Mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads, Toppings, as a seasoning
	(4) Tofu	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Stir Fry, Gratin, Salad
	(5) Rice basmati	Steaming	4°C for up to 3 days	Arancini di riso

DIRECTIONS

Peel and quarter onions and cook them in water, in such an amount to cover them, refill some water if necessary. Cook until soft and sweet. Add the tomatoes and blend. Slowly cook on little heat for at least 2 hours, the longer the better. Traditional Indian **(1) curry sauce** can be almost infinite when properly refilled.

Steam and chill the prepared **(2) vegetables (carrot, parsley root and turnip)**, mix the spices to taste and blend the **(3) coriander-green** with neutral oil. Cook or steam the **(5) rice basmati** with cardamom and cinnamon. Drain the **(4) tofu** and fry on medium heat without oil until lightly golden. Add marinade and reduce until coated.

Take a ladle from the sauce and season to taste with your personal curry mixture and salt, add (soy) cream and (vegan) butter to taste. Add warm Tofu and sorted veggies.

Serve with fair-trade Basmati-Rice and top off with coriander-chutney.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 pot of sauce 1 Tray of veggies, preferably sorted 1 Tray of prepared Tofu 1 Tray of Rice 1 Bowl of chutney	Keep veggies and sauce separated until necessary to mix so the vegetables don't overcook in the hot sauce. Serve Rice apart. One dish is approximately 360 g and contains 180 g of Rice, 100 ml of sauce and 80 g of veggies and Tofu.	In this dish, every kind of vegetable can be used. Every season makes it's own Curry. Every Chef has their own Curry-Mixture. In India there is no «Curry-Powder».

QUANTITY

QUALITY

BALANCED
INTAKE

MICRO

POSITIVE
EMOTIONS

MACRO

NUTRIENTS

Protein Transition

Now more than ever, we need to question the quality of the food we eat. The simplest approach is to consider the issue from a chemical perspective: every day, we consume millions of molecules to nourish ourselves - molecules that give taste, aroma, smell, colours and textures but above all energy and support the functioning of our organism. However, the issue becomes more complicated on a global scale when we are asked to make virtuous choices and learn to distinguish between food quality and the environmental and health implications of our consumption.

Following the One-Health approach, it is becoming more important to focus on healthier and more sustainable diets that meet our nutritional needs.

This means that every time we buy, transport, process, serve and eat food, we should think about it as a complex system of molecules. We should think about where the food comes from, what quality it is, how much we are buying and the economic and social effects of eating it. In this context, it is important to eat less meat and other animal products, and to think about other ways to get the nutrients we need and different types of protein that we could add to our diet.

The objective of this chapter is to explore the potential for novel insights into the realm of protein intake by means of illuminating exemplars. The broad spectrum of properties exhibited by legumes has resulted in a preponderance of research focusing on recipes that incorporate them.

The primary strategies for progressive exposure adopted to increase the intake of alternative proteins in the recipes in this chapter

are listed below, with the aim of ensuring and supporting the acceptance of “new” ingredients by children:

- adaptation of well-known recipes constitutes an important aspect of the culinary experience, with examples including **Hungarian green peas soup with nokedli**, which serves as a good example of a balanced dish rooted in local culture, and the imitation of familiar sensory profiles, as evidenced by the reinterpretation of **Beuschel with mixed mushrooms**;
- employment of cognitive anchors and camouflaging techniques is recommended, as evidenced in the preparation of **Lentil croquettes and fennel salad**. These dishes effectively utilise their popular rounded shape and the contrast of crunchy and soft textures;
- offer of alternative variations (in appearance, choice of ingredients) for well-known dishes. Illustrative examples of this approach include **Vegetable couscous with smoked tofu** or **Mushroom Adobada, Ingrid green peas and flatbread**;
- intrigue with unconventional scenarios, as in the case of a sweet snack (see **Brownies & Blondies**).

You can explore these topics in the second chapter of the *School Menu Design Handbook*, entitled *Progressive Exposure and Circular Cuisine*, specifically pages 68 (One Health approach), 75 (protein transition), and 86, 87, 117, 118, 119 and 120 (progressive exposure strategies).

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Vienna,
Austria

Saša Asanović, Julia Haas,
Andrea Vaz-König

Beuschel with mixed mushrooms

Vienna,
Austria

Saša Asanović, Julia Haas,
Andrea Vaz-König

Brownies & Blondies

Lyon,
France

Martin Charlotte, Estelle Jacque

Chickpea and rice curry

Lyon,
France

Martin Charlotte, Estelle Jacque

**Coquillettes with lentils, mushrooms
and curry**

Budapest,
Hungary

Andras Bittsanszky, Eszter Faki,
Éva Kinorányi, Orsolya Diófási-Kovács

Hungarian green peas soup with nokedli

Slovakia

Eva Blaho, Katarina Medvedova,
Lubos Mego

Lentil and carrot stew

Milan,
Italy

Chiara Mandelli, Cristina Sossan,
Elena Fucile, Diego Capocci

Lentils croquettes and fennel salad

Copenhagen,
Denmark

Søren Buhl Steiniche, Astrid Dahl,
Ebbe Engdal Skovfoged, Emil Kiær
Lund, Christian Rune Jensen

**Mushroom Adobada, Ingrid green peas
and flatbread**

Slovakia

Eva Blaho, Katarina Medvedova,
Lubos Mego

Vegetable couscous with smoked tofu

Beuschel with mixed mushrooms

TYPE OF DISH

Stew & ragout

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Vienna, Austria

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Children can learn how to approach traditional dishes, such as a grandparent's offal dishes, which they do not normally enjoy. A learning module on the history of ancient recipes can be carried out, involving interviews and book researches.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Offer an attractive, tasty and innovative plant-based alternative to a classic Austrian meat dish, retaining the familiar flavours and textures that make up the dish's character.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
Lactose Free
Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	546	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	18	(% of total)
Fibre Content	6.7	(grams)
Sodium	2.6	(grams)
Sugars	5.9	(grams)
Saturated Fats	5.3	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	7
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Stock, vegetable	100	15	150	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	9	-
Seitan	23.3%	3.5	35	2.1	0.7	0.5	0.7	69.3	-
Mushroom, Oyster	20%	3	30	1.5	<0.1	0.2	0.1	5.4	-
Onion, red, raw	6.7%	1	10	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	3.7	-
Carrot, raw	6.7%	1	10	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	3.2	-
Carrot, raw, yellow	6.7%	1	10	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	3.2	-
Flour, wheat, wholemeal	4%	0.6	6	10.3	<0.1	5.4	0.3	19.8	-
Oil, sunflower, seed	4%	0.6	6	-	-	-	10.6	53.82	-
Gherkins, sour, pickled	2.7%	0.4	4	0.9	0.3	1	-	0.4	-
Mustard	2%	0.3	3	3	1.4	2.7	0.4	3.87	-
Capers	2%	0.3	3	3.2	3	0.4	0.2	1.29	-
Miso, soya, paste	1.3%	0.2	2	6.6	5	6	0.7	2.6	-
Vinegar	1.3%	0.2	2	-	<0.1	0.6	-	0.44	-
Parsley, fresh	1.3%	0.2	2	5	<0.1	-	0.1	0.74	-
Garlic, raw	0.7%	0.1	1	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	1.58	-
Salt	0.7%	0.1	1	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Thyme, fresh	0.7%	0.1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Celery, raw	0.3%	<0.1	0.5	1.1	<0.1	1	-	<0.1	-
Pepper, black/white	-	<0.1	<0.1	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	0.16	-
Lemon, fresh, juice	-	-	<0.1	0.3	<0.1	2	-	<0.1	-
Croutons	41.7%	6.25	62.5	4	1	3.8	6.7	307	-
Soy, milk	41.7%	6.25	62.5	1.1	<0.1	1.7	0.2	18	-
Rice, flour	8%	1.2	12	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	42.24	-
Salt	1.3%	0.2	2	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION

Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Vegetables stock	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Ragout, Sauces
(2) Vegetable velouté	Boiling + mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Every spiced dishes
(3) Brown roux	Dry cooking	4°C for up to 3 days	Pies and desserts
(4) Bread dumplings	Mixing + shaping + steaming	4°C for up to 3 days	Croutons for soup
(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Beuschel: use the peels of the root vegetables to prepare a **(1) Stock, vegetable** and cook the seitan and mushrooms in it. Cut the root vegetables into julienne stripes and blanch them in the Stock, vegetable. Prepare a **(3) brown roux** and add diced onion. Add chopped garlic, capers, pickles, and thyme, and sauté them together. Deglaze with the Stock, vegetable and make a **(2) velouté**. Cut the seitan and mushrooms into julienne stripes as well. Add all the ingredients to the velouté and season with miso, mustard, salt, and pepper. Finish with a splash of vinegar, lemon zest, and fresh parsley.

(4) Bread dumplings: bring the Soy, milk to a boil with the spices. Mix the bread cubes with the Rice, flour and pour the spiced Soy, milk over them, mixing well. Let the mixture rest for about 30 minutes. Shape into rolls using cling film and cook or steam for approximately 30 minutes.

You can finishing with a drop of of plantbased sourcream.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 large pot of Beuschel 1 tray of dumplings	200 gr of Beuschel. 50 gr of bread dumpling.	Transformed recipe of a traditional dish from Vienna. Can also be made gluten-free.

Brownies & Blondies

TYPE OF DISH

Dessert

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Vienna, Austria

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Use of legumes workshop

Exploring legumes, their global culinary traditions, and health benefits. Pupils participants compare protein sources based on taste, preparation, environmental impact, and water use. The session includes hands-on cooking and baking with legumes.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Protein transition away from meat to pulses and legumes needs to be supported. Especially sweet dishes could benefit from higher protein. **#lateralthinking**

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	1608	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	9	(% of total)
Fibre Content	41.5	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	51.7	(grams)
Saturated Fats	44.1	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
for Brownies									
Beans, white, boiled	100	1.13	90	9.9	<0.1	0.6	0.2	101.7	-
Chocolate, dark, sugar-free	55.6%	0.63	50	14.7	<0.1	0.7	20	227	-
Almonds, skin, unsalted	22.2%	0.25	20	10.2	<0.1	4.4	3.6	124.4	-
Oil, coconut	13.3%	0.15	12	-	-	-	83.7	107	-
Sugar, brown	13.3%	0.15	12	-	<0.1	99	-	47.52	-
Oat, bran	4.4%	<0.1	4	15.4	<0.1	1.5	1.2	14.68	-
Apple, sauce, tinned	4.4%	<0.1	4	1.9	<0.1	17.1	-	3.04	-
Chestnuts, flour	4.4%	<0.1	4	4.1	<0.1	6	0.5	7.56	-
Baking powder	4.4%	<0.1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salt	0.8%	0.1	0.75	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

for Blondies									
Chickpeas, boiled	133.3%	1.5	120	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	165.6	-
Syrup, maple	62.2%	0.7	56	-	-	60.7	-	150.6	-
Chocolate, dark, sugar-free	55.6%	0.63	50	14.7	<0.1	0.7	20	227	-
Butter, peanuts, salt	28.9%	0.33	26	8.6	<0.1	5.7	7.1	158.8	-
Almonds, skin, salted	22.2%	0.25	20	10.2	0.2	4.4	3.6	124.4	-
Rice, flour	13.3%	0.15	12	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	42.24	-
Oil, coconut	13.3%	0.15	12	-	-	-	83.7	107	-
Baking powder	4.4%	<0.1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salt	-	-	-	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Kidney Beans		Soaking + boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads, spreads, stews
(2) Chickpeas		Soaking + boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Fritters and spreads
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Brownies
Melt the chocolate and coconut oil, then mix with the cooked beans. Mix all the other ingredients together and combine with the bean-chocolate mixture. Spread evenly in a tray. Sprinkle the chopped nuts and chocolate over the surface. Bake at 180°C for 30 minutes.

Blondies
Puree the chickpeas and mix with all the other ingredients. Sprinkle the chopped nuts and chocolate over the surface. Bake at 200°C for 30 minutes.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 GN Blondies 1 GN Brownies	100 pieces per 1 GN. 2x25 gr per piece.	Legumes for sweet tooth - dessert with high nutritional value. Gluten free (if gf oats are used).

Chickpea and rice curry

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Lyon, France

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Showcase the products

In the nursery restaurant so that children can discover them before eating the meal. Using sensory chickpea bags to let kids explore their senses while they play with it.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Introducing pulses in nursery menus one time per week, and in different shapes and ways in order to diversify protein sources.

#progressiveexposure

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	255	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	6	(% of total)
Fibre Content	8	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	2.4	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.9	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	3
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Chickpeas, boiled	100	0.75	75	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	103.5	-
Tomatoes, tinned	66.7%	0.5	50	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	12	-
Rice, white, raw	33.3%	0.25	25	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	88	-
Onion, red, raw	10.7%	<0.1	8	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	2.96	-
Oil, sunflower, seed	5.3%	<0.1	4	-	-	-	10.6	35.8	-
Paprika, powder	2.7%	<0.1	2	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	7.18	-
Coriander	2%	<0.1	1.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cumin, seed, dried	1.3%	<0.1	1	10.5	0.2	-	1.9	4.27	-
Garlic, raw	0.7%	<0.1	0.5	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	0.8	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Chickpeas curry	Braising (dry + wet) cooking	4°C for up to 3 days	Chickpeas purée, fritters or spreads
	(2) Rice	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Rice salad
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Brown garlic and onions in oil, then add the tomato coulis and cooked chickpeas. Let them cook for about 20 minutes. Add the cumin, paprika, a bit of pepper and a glass of water. Stir the mixture and let it cook for extra 20 minutes. Cook the **(2) rice** in salted water apart. Then out of fire, add the coriander on the **(1) chickpea curry**.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 large pot with chickpea curry 1 tray with boiled rice	Let the rice and the chickpea base separated so the children can choose to mix themselves. 75 gr of each chickpea curry. 75 gr of boiled rice.	Be careful of the temperature and let kids explore their meal.

Coquillettes with lentils, mushrooms and curry

TYPE OF DISH

Pasta & lasagne

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Lyon, France

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Children could visit a farm / producer (lentils, pasta). It could be interesting to propose the recipe according to the different seasons. Showcase the products / vegetables (mushrooms, lentils,...) in the school restaurant and children can discover them before eating the meal.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

A vegetarian recipe with seasonal ingredients, served during "the taste week" (a reference French food education event that takes place every year in october, aiming to sensibelize about the school meal).

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	316	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	18	(% of total)
Fibre Content	7	(grams)
Sodium	0.7	(grams)
Sugars	3.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.7	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Pasta, wholemeal, raw	100	100	54	6.9	<0.1	3.5	0.3	188	-
Tomatoes, tinned	50%	50	27	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	6.48	-
Mushroom, raw	27.8%	27.78	15	1.5	<0.1	0.2	0.1	2.7	-
Lentils, green/brown, dried	27.8%	27.78	15	18	<0.1	1	0.3	45.6	-
Coriander	9.3%	9.26	5	-	-	-	-	<0.1	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	7.4%	7.41	4	-	-	-	14.9	36	-
Cream	5.6%	5.56	3	-	<0.1	3.1	23	10.17	-
Onion, red, raw	5.6%	5.56	3	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	1.11	-
Rice, flour	5.6%	5.56	3	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	10.5	-
Salt	4%	4	2.16	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Oil, sunflower, seed	2.6%	2.59	1.4	-	-	-	10.6	12.55	-
Garlic, raw	1.9%	1.85	1	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	1.58	-
Canned, curry	0.6%	0.56	0.3	3.5	-	0.25	-	0.81	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1)	Lentils-mushrooms curry base	Braising (dry + wet cooking)	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups and and fillings
(2)	Pasta	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Any other pasta dish or even salads and fritters
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS For (1) **lentils-mushrooms-curry base** brown garlic and onions in oil, then add the curry, crushed tomatoes, sliced bottom mushrooms, lentils with the salt. Let it cook. Out of fire, mix the Rice, flour with cold water, to obtain a smooth / creamy paste. Mix it with the rest of the mixture and let cook for 5 more minutes. Then out of fire, add the coriander and cream. Adjust seasoning if needed. Pair it with cooked (2) **pasta**.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Let the pasta and the lentils base separated so the children can choose to mix themselves.	100 gr of lentil base. 150 gr of pasta. 250 gr in total per child.	This dish is ideal for vegetarian meals. This recipe could be done with a variety of vegetables, according to the current season.

Hungarian green pea soup with nokedli

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Budapest, Hungary

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Green pea

For all age groups: collecting folk traditions related to green pea.
For younger children: making pictures from green pea and other seeds using gluing techniques.
For all students: mashing green peas.

Nokedli workshop

A deep dive into the origins of this masterpiece and its materic tool.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Green peas are an excellent source of protein and are part of traditional Hungarian cuisine, so children are familiar with them.

This soup is an excellent choice as part of a balanced diet, as it supports proper digestion and helps maintain a healthy immune system.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	349	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	22	(% of total)
Fibre Content	17.8	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	6.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	8
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Peas, green, dried	100	8	80	20,4	<0.1	6	0.7	252	-
Carrot, raw	18.8%	1.5	15	2,8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	4.8	10
Flour	18.8%	1.5	15	3,2	<0.1	1.1	0.2	50.25	-
Turnip, raw	12.5%	1	10	2,7	<0.1	4.6	-	3.1	10
Onions, raw	6.3%	0.5	5	2,7	<0.1	4.5	0.1	1.85	15
Egg, whole, chicken, raw	6.3%	0.5	5	-	0.2	0.2	3.1	6.6	20
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3.8%	0.3	3	-	-	-	14.9	27	-
Paprika, ground	1.3%	0.1	1	20,9	<0.1	-	1.7	3.6	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Vegetable base	Braising (dry + wet cooking)	4°C for up to 3 days	Used in soups, vegetable stews or alongside starchy side dishes
	(2) Nokedli	Mixing the dough and after drop to the soup	Used straight away	Can be used in any kind of soups, similar to spaetzle
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

For the **(1) vegetable base**, toast chopped onion in oil until translucent, add peeled and diced vegetables and cook over a low heat keeping on stirring. Sprinkle over the flour and paprika, stir to combine, sauté briefly then add plenty of Stock, vegetable (or water). Bring to a boil while stirring. Add the green peas, the peppers and parsley greens and let it simmer until everything is fully cooked.

For the **(2) nokedli** (drizzled noodle) mix the egg with the flour. Use a traditional nokedli maker or a large-hole grater and place over the pot. Add some dough to the top and letting the small pieces drop into the boiling soup. Once the dumplings float to the surface (about 2-3 minutes), let them cook for another 1-2 minutes.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Cooking pot	Serve in soup plate with spoon. Put to the top fresh parsley. 300 ml per portion.	This is a very popular plant-based soup in Hungary, which is also loved by children. This soup is rich in plant-based protein, fiber and vitamins.

Lentil and carrot stew

TYPE OF DISH

Stew & ragout

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Slovakia

SEASON(S)
OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED
EDUCATIONAL
EXPERIENCE

Learning to like legumes

Are you familiar with this dish?

Guess which legumes are in this dish. Guess as many ingredients of the recipe as you can. Discuss which one you like the most and try to come up with at least one name of the dish for each type of ingredient.

KEYWORDS AND
COMMUNICATED
VALUES

*>why I am preparing
this dish*

This recipe helps to teach the preparation of a classic lentil-based dish, emphasizing the use of legumes as a source of plant-based protein, carbs and fibers. It promotes sustainable eating habits and balanced nutrition for various age groups.

INCLUSION
AND ALLERGENS

*> for whom I am
preparing this dish*

GLUTEN FREE

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY:
NUTRITIONAL
PROFILE
PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	283	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	24	(% of total)
Fibre Content	12.2	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	6.7	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE:
ENVIRONMENTAL
AND SOCIAL
PROFILE

Main Ingredients	12
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Lentils, green/brown, dried	100	5.5	55	18	<0.1	1	0.3	168.3	-
Carrot, raw	63.6%	3.5	35	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	11.2	20
Potato, sweet, raw	63.6%	3.5	35	2.4	<0.1	5.5	0.1	31.85	20
Yogurt Greek skimmed	54.5%	3	30	-	<0.1	5	-	16.8	-
Onion, red, raw	7.6%	0.4	4.2	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	1.55	10
Oil, olive, extra virgin	7.3%	0.4	4	-	-	-	14.9	36	-
Garlic, raw	2.4%	0.1	1.3	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	2.05	15
Paprika, powder	1.8%	0.1	1	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	3.6	-
Salt	1.8%	0.1	1	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Turmeric	1.8%	0.1	1	-	-	100	-	-	-
Cumin, seed, dried	1.8%	0.1	1	10.5	0.2	-	1.9	4.27	-
Butter, unsalted	1.8%	0.1	1	-	<0.1	1.1	53.6	7.37	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Lentils		Soaking + simmering	4°C for up to 3 days	Side dish to meatballs, vegetables, sausages, or grilled meats
(2) Spicy Sautéed vegetables		Braising (dry + wet cooking)	4°C for up to 3 days	Base, thickener or a vegetable addition to any stews, soups, purees or sauces, with or without the garlic and spices
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Soak and cook **(1) lentils** with bay leaf until they are tender. In a separate pot, pan fry the diced onion in oil until translucent, then add carrots and sweet potatoes cut into small pieces. Season with crushed garlic, salt, turmeric, cumin and toast the **(2) vegetables** all together. Gradually stir in hot water (or vegetable broth) and bring the mixture to a simmer. When the vegetables are soft, blend half of them into a creamy mixture. Add the cooked lentils, let it simmer until the flavors combine. Stir in the butter for richness and adjust seasoning to taste. Serve warm with small portion of white yoghurt and a pinch of smoked paprika if desired, garnish with parsley and pair with egg if desired.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Buffet or plated service with side options like bread, meat or egg	Portion weight: 240 gr Serving temperature: hot Serving tools: bowl and spoon Service: immediately after preparation for the best texture and flavor Holding: keep warm in a steam table; yogurt has to be kept aside and cooled.	The dish is rich in plant-based protein and fiber, making it a great main course or side dish. Perfect for pairing with smoked meats or vegetarian options like roasted vegetables, eggs or baked tofu.

Lentils croquettes and fennel salad

TYPE OF DISH

Patties & galette

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Milan, Italy

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Introducing the main raw materials to the kids through an hackathon for kids. Presenting the products and taking the kids to the kitchen to get familiar with infrastructures and equipments. After that, asking kids to invent a recipe with the legumes and other products used in the menu.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Easy, healthy and sustainable. The Milano municipality catering service is introducing legume recipes to make children more familiar with these ingredients.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	190	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	8	(% of total)
Fibre Content	5.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.3	(grams)
Sugars	2.4	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	12
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Fennel, raw	100	112	56	2.4	<0.1	2	-	9.52	35
Potatoes, raw	46.4%	52	26	1.8	<0.1	1	-	22.88	-
Cheese, asiago	28.6%	32	16	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lentils, red, dried	28.6%	32	16	18	<0.1	1	0.3	49	-
Bread, wheat, rye, wholemeal	19.6%	22	11	7.2	0.4	2.3	0.4	25.74	-
Carrot, raw	12.5%	14	7	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	2.24	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	10.7%	12	6	-	-	-	14.9	54	-
Onion, red, raw	8.9%	10	5	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	1.85	-
Cheese, Parmigiano Reggiano	8.9%	10	5	-	1	-	17.6	20.2	-
Egg, whole, chicken, raw	5.9%	6.6	3.3	-	0.1	0.2	3.1	4.35	-
Vinegar	1.8%	2	1	-	<0.1	0.6	-	0.22	-
Salt	1.3%	1.4	0.7	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Croquettes starchy base		Wet cooking + chilling	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, broths and velliutes
(2) Croquettes dough		Shaping and breading	Freezing temp.	
(3) Fennel		Finely chopping	4°C for up to 3 days	Julienned fennel could be used (not seasoned) for cream soups as a first course
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Cook all the (1) **starches** at once as follows: in salted boiling water diced potato, carrot, onions and lentils all together and let it chill. Once chilled, add to grated Asiago cheese or organic/caciotta cheese, parmigiano reggiano cheese, grated stale bread and pasteurized organic eggs. Mix well the (2) **croquettes dough** and let it chill again. Shape or extrude the croquettes, and bread them. Bake the croquettes in oven and finally serve with a finely sliced and season raw (3) **fennel**.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
The product is cooked in the kitchens and shipped hot. In the canteen it is just served on a plate.	One dish contains 3 croquettes and 1 portion of fennels.	The fresh raw fennel salad gives a crunchy twist to the hot croquettes, enhancing the palatability.
1 warm tray of croquettes 1 of fennels to serve the dish directly at the table or self service line		

Mushroom Adobada, Ingrid green peas and flatbread

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Copenhagen, Denmark

SEASON(S)
OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED
EDUCATIONAL
EXPERIENCE

“Green food for the eye and mouth”

Making colorful food with lots of greens for the eye.
Playing around with different structures in the food exploring eating with your hands meals.

KEYWORDS AND
COMMUNICATED
VALUES

*>why I am preparing
this dish*

- Showcase sustainable food, with warmth and flavors.
- Making the tasting experience fun and the greens as a comforting substitution for meat.
- Showcasing a now product (kebab/kofte) in a green way.

INCLUSION
AND ALLERGENS

*> for whom I am
preparing this dish*

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY:
NUTRITIONAL
PROFILE
PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	293	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	66	(% of total)
Fibre Content	5.7	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	4.5	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.3	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE:
ENVIRONMENTAL
AND SOCIAL
PROFILE

Main Ingredients	3
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Brussel sprouts, raw	100	0.3	30	4.1	<0.1	1.4	0.1	13.8	20
Semolina	100	0.3	30	2	<0.1	3	0.3	101	-
Mushroom, Oyster	83.3%	0.25	25	1.5	<0.1	0.2	0.1	4.5	10
Pepper, sweet, red, raw	83.3%	0.25	25	1.8	<0.1	4.3	-	6.25	10
Celeriac, raw	83.3%	0.25	25	4.9	<0.1	-	-	9.5	25
Peas, Ingrid	83.3%	0.25	25	4.7	<0.1	6	0.8	89.75	-
Carrot, raw	40%	0.12	12	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	3.84	7.5
Oil, olive, extra virgin	20%	0.6	6	-	-	-	14.9	54	-
Oregano, dried	6.7%	<0.1	2	15	<0.1	-	2.1	7.2	-
Garlic, raw	6.7%	<0.1	2	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	3.16	11

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Flatbread		Boiling + kneaking + baking	Freezing	Pitas, croutons
(2) Adobada marinade mix		Mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Dip, mole, soup base
(3) Skewers		Composing and roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Veggie kebab, stews
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

For the **(1) flatbread**, cook the peas in salted boiling water (or veggie stock with plenty of bay leaves and onion). Strain and blitz into a solid paste. Choose a strong flour and mix your bread dough with water, olive oil, salt and the split pea paste (optional: use sourdough). Roast the bread on a pan. For the **(2) adobada marinade mix**, mix extra virgin olive oil, oregano and chopped garlic and let it sit at room temperature.

(3) Skewers: tear the oyster mushrooms, cut the bell pepper, celeriac, brussel sprout and carrot and marinade for minimum 2 hours with the adobada mix. Put your skewers into cold water so they doesn't burn/brown. When ready, grill in oven on 220°C for about 20 min, full fan.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Flat plate, fork, napkin. Portioned, but serve as sharefood on community plates.	It can be sticky, so remember napkins for the kids.	Add your adobada mushroom and greens to your flatbread and enjoy.
1 tray of skewers 1 tray of flatbread	Around 250 gr per portion.	

Vegetable couscous with smoked tofu

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Bratislava, Slovakia

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Be strong enough

Do you practise sports regularly? Be smart and come up with high protein meals for yourself. Eggs and meat are fine, but you probably won't be eating it every day. Have you heard of plant proteins? Try our couscous with tofu and come up with more dishes with plant based proteins. And there are few questions for you. Do you know what tofu is actually made of? And in which country of the world do they use it the most?

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Learn about creating balanced, plant-based meals with seasonal vegetables and protein-rich tofu in a simple, healthy recipe.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	336	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	11	(% of total)
Fibre Content	9.5	(grams)
Sodium	0.5	(grams)
Sugars	3.6	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.5	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	7
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Stock, vegetable	100	13	130	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	7.8	-
Tofu, smoked	100	8.5	85	2	<0.1	0.5	0.8	101.15	-
Pepper, sweet, red, raw	27.7%	3.6	36	1.8	<0.1	4.3	-	9	20
Couscous, wholemeal, unprepared	26.9%	3.5	35	8.4	<0.1	2.4	0.3	119.7	-
Peas, raw	24.6%	3.2	32	4.7	<0.1	1	-	20.8	-
Chickpeas, boiled	22.3%	2.9	29	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	40	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3.1%	0.4	4	-	-	-	14.9	36	-
Lemon, fresh, juice	2.7%	0.35	3.5	0.3	<0.1	2	-	1.64	50
Salt	0.1%	<0.1	0.12	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Curry, powder	<0.1	-	<0.1	25	<0.1	-	1.6	0.11	-
Paprika, powder	<0.1	-	<0.1	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	0.10	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Brown Stock	Roasting + simmering	4°C for up to 3 days, frozen for up to 3 months	Base for soups and broth to cook starches and vegetables in
	(2) Couscous	Stirred with boiling hot broth	4°C for up to 3 days	Used instead of traditional rice in dishes to promote versatility
	(3) Sautéed vegetables	Roasting	Vacuumed 4°C for up to 5 days	Used for many other recipes as a possible side
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Prepare a **(1) brown stock** with all the vegetable scraps available roasted and then infused in water. Let it simmer for 2 hours. Dice the smoked tofu and fry it in olive oil until it is golden brown. **(3) Sautéed vegetables** adding diced colorful bell peppers, peas, and cooked chickpeas to the tofu. Season with garam masala and smoked paprika, and cook until the vegetables are tender. Add the **(2) couscous** and pour in the Stock, vegetable broth. Let it simmer until the couscous absorbs the broth and is soft. Season the dish with salt and finish with lemon juice for a fresh touch. Garnish with freshly chopped parsley before serving.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 only tray of couscous Serving tools: flat plates and a fork Service type: buffet or plated service, garnished with fresh parsley	Portion weight: 310 gr. Serve immediately after preparation for the best flavor and texture. Holding: the dish can be kept warm in a steam table for service, but couscous should not be held for extended periods to avoid sogginess.	This dish is ideal for vegetarian or vegan menus and caters well to individuals seeking plant-based meals. Ensure the couscous is not overcooked to maintain a light, fluffy texture.

LEGUMES

ALTERNATIVE

PROTEIN

PROGRESSIVE
FOOD
EXPOSURE

COGNITIVE
ANCHORS

ONE
HEALTH

CAMOUFLAGE

CAMOUFLAGE

Adaptive recipes

When moving from theory to practice, the transition is not always smooth. This is what can happen in the process of designing and developing recipes and menus: in theory, they may seem coherent and work very well, but the end result may fall short of expectations. It is well known that the enjoyment of a dish is the result of a complex evaluation process, guided and influenced by both individual and environmental factors. Furthermore, the evaluation of a dish is not a binary (black or white) process, especially when factors such as familiarity come into play. In order to support dietitians and chefs in the development of new recipes, it is advisable to focus on those that, based on experience, have proven to achieve satisfactory results.

These elements can form the starting point for subsequent modular transformation, both in terms of composition and presentation. From this perspective, the concept of the adaptive recipe emerges, understood as the ability of a recipe to adapt to different contexts while ensuring the same final enjoyment.

These recipes can be useful in a variety of situations, for example:

- meeting specific dietary requirements, such as recipes that are free from major allergens or have the potential to become so. **Sweet potato ducats with creamy spinach and tempeh cubes**, as well as **Coca de calabaza**, are both examples of recipes designed to be (easily transformed into) vegan, lactose-free and gluten-free;
- ensuring continuity throughout the seasons: as in the case of **Potatoes, Curd, Linseed Oil, raw seasonal vegetable sticks**, where both potatoes and raw vegetable sticks can be easily replaced with similar alternatives that share the same crunchy texture;

- creating familiarity through the adoption of an approach that involves taking certain elements from familiar combinations and integrating them into new contexts. A good example of this are popular sauces, commonly used to accompany chips or meat, which in this context are offered in new combinations: **Crispy vegetables and tempeh with miso-mayo**, **Red curry with vegetables and edamame**, and finally, **Baked seasonal veggies with beetroot ketchup**;
- for modulating the final texture of a single dish by varying the water content, which can range from a salad to a soup or broth. This method, combined with a variation in serving temperature, ensures the continuity of a recipe throughout the different seasons. The last example mentioned is particularly effective for gradually introducing students to certain stimuli over the course of a school year.

You can explore in greater depth by reading the second chapter, *Progressive Presentation and Circular Cooking*, of the *School Menu Design Handbook* on pages 86, 87, 117, 118, 119 and 120 for progressive presentation strategies.

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**Nürnberg
and Essen,
Germany**

Alice Baumgärtner, Manuel Poschadel,
Christian Sandner, Stephanie Schielein,
Karin Schmidt, Vera Stöbel

**Baked seasonal veggies
with beetroot ketchup**

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**Tallinn,
Estonia**

Kadri Ausmaa, Kendra Kairi Vaino,
Kristi Tiido

Cauliflower – Chickpea soup

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**Copenhagen,
Denmark**

Søren Buhl Steiniche, Astrid Dahl,
Ebbe Engdal Skovfoged, Emil Kiær
Lund, Christian Rune Jensen

**Crispy vegetables and tempeh
with miso-mayo**

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**Nürnberg
and Essen,
Germany**

Alice Baumgärtner, Manuel Poschadel,
Christian Sandner, Stephanie Schielein,
Karin Schmidt, Vera Stöbel

**Potatoes, curd, linseed oil,
raw seasonal vegetable sticks**

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**Valencia,
Spain**

Cristina Ruiz, Paloma Vicent,
Paola Hernandez, Hector Muelas,
Joachim Pomeu Mateus

Pumpkin cake / Coca de calabaza

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**Copenhagen,
Denmark**

Søren Buhl Steiniche, Astrid Dahl,
Ebbe Engdal Skovfoged, Emil Kiær
Lund, Christian Rune Jensen

**Red curry with vegetables
and edamame**

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**Vienna,
Austria**

Andrea Vaz-König, Julia Haas,
Saša Asanović

**Sweet potato ducats with creamy spinach
and tempeh cubes**

Baked seasonal veggies and beetroot ketchup

TYPE OF DISH

Patties & gallettes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Nürnberg and Essen, Germany

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Children prefer to be able to choose which veggie they like to try, do not mix and mingle. Everybody loves ketchup, so let's make our own.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

- It's easy and fast
- It can be varied in every season
- Ketchup can be done with fruity vegetable or fruit (plum, apple, pepper, etc.)

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	292	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	46	(% of total)
Fibre Content	7.7	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	9.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.7	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	9
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Potatoes, raw	100	18.75	150	1.8	<0.1	1	-	132	15
Tomatoes, tinned	26.7%	5	40	0.7	<0.1	3.6	0.1	9.6	-
Pumpkin, raw	26.7%	5	40	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	5.6	25
Onion, red, raw	20%	3.75	30	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	11.1	25
Beetroot, raw	20%	3.75	30	2.9	<0.1	6	-	11.4	25
Carrot, raw	20%	3.75	30	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	9.6	25
Cabbage, red, raw	20%	3.75	30	3.6	<0.1	3	-	8.1	30
Oil, olive, extra-virgin	6.7%	1.25	10	-	-	-	14.9	90	-
Brussel sprouts, raw	6.7%	1.25	10	4.1	<0.1	1.4	0.1	4.6	10
Garlic, cooked, fat	1.3%	0.25	2	2.7	<0.1	1.4	-	2.54	-
Papika, powder	0.7%	0.13	1	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	3.6	-
Oregano, dried	0.7%	0.13	1	15	<0.1	-	2.1	3.6	-
Salt	0.3%	<0.1	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Biodiverse vegetables		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Could be used in a curry sauce or in vegetable pan with rice or just a side-dish
(2) Beetroot Ketchup		Boiling + blending	Pasteurized, in dry storage	Some people could eat everything with ketchup
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

(1) **Organic vegetable** can only be washed, most don't have to be peeled, which is healthy for the body and the wallet. Cut and coat the veggies with spices and temperature stable olive oil. After baking finish off with a sprinkle of lemon juice (to taste). Bake the vegetable sorted on trays, to be able to put the vegetable that cook faster, later into the oven. (first go the carrots and potatoes, then come the Onions and sprouts and pumpkin, at last put in the cabbage). Also keep them separated, so the children can choose which vegetables to try and eat and which not. For the (2) **ketchup**, peel and roughly cut the onion and slowly cook them in Oil, olive, extra-virgin. Wash, cut and cook the beetroot in as least water as possible to not lose taste in the water (it should be salted). Add beetroot and canned tomatoes to the onions, blend everything and season with salt, pepper, balsamic vinegar.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Several trays of sorted vegetables 1 bowl of ketchup	Ideally kids can choose which kind of veggies they want in their dish. One dish is approximately 360 gr: 130 gr of veggies, 150 gr of potatoes and 80 gr of ketchup.	Almost all veggies can be used. Here we show, how carrots, cabbages and potatoes can be used. In spring we could use zucchini, green beans and asparagus.

Cauliflower - Chickpea soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Tallinn, Estonia

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Get to know Estonian legumes

Exploring Estonian biodiversity and seasonality through researching traditional productions. Pairing traditional productions with other gastronomic cultures as in this recipe - the case of the curry.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Encouraging students to try new tastes. Plus, the cauliflower can be easily substitute with pumpkin with which it share similar starch composition. Moreover by cooking the pumpkin with the skin, we can reduce the loss. This still give a creamy texture.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- VEGETARIAN**
- Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	174	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	13	(% of total)
Fibre Content	7.2	(grams)
Sodium	1.2	(grams)
Sugars	3.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	5.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	3
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Stock, vegetable	100	1	10	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	6	-
Cauliflower, raw	50%	0.50	50	2.2	<0.1	2.4	-	12.5	2
Chickpeas, boiled	50%	0.50	50	8.8	<0.1	0.3	0.4	69	-
Coconut, milk	35%	0.35	35	0.5	<0.1	1.5	15.2	60.5	-
Carrot, raw	15%	0.15	15	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	4.8	20
Onion, red, raw	8%	<0.1	8	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	2.96	20
Lemon, juice, fresh	8%	<0.1	8	0.3	<0.1	2	-	3.76	-
Salt	2.5%	<0.1	2.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Curry, powder	2.5%	<0.1	2.5	25	<0.1	-	1.6	9.25	-
Ginger, root	2.5%	<0.1	2.5	2	<0.1	1.7	0.2	2	-
Garlic, raw	2%	<0.1	2	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	3.16	16
Parsley, fresh	1.2%	<0.1	1.2	5	<0.1	-	0.1	0.44	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Boiled chickpeas		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Vegetable stew
(2) Stock, vegetable		Roasting + simmering	4°C for up to 3 days	Soup and sauces
(3) Sauteed veggies		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, stews, patties
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

(1) **Boil the chickpeas** soaked the day before. Peel the carrot, onion and garlic.

Dice the onion, mince the garlic and grate carrot.

Heat the pot and (3) **sauteé the vegetables** a few minutes.

Add (2) **Stock, vegetable** and bring to a boil. Cut cauliflower into small pieces and add into the pot and cook until the soft. Add chickpeas, ground ginger, curry and Coconut, milk.

Boil 5 minutes, puree with the blender until smooth. Season with salt and lemon juice.

Garnish with parsley and serve.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
½ 100 GN tray	Soup plate 250 ml and spoon.	Can serve with croutons or fresh bread.

Crispy vegetables and tempeh with miso-mayo

TYPE OF DISH

Vegetable & legumes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Copenhagen, Denmark

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

The plant-mayo experience!

A workshop on using alternatives to make mayo sauces: using any kind of plant based milk (oats, almond, rice), seaweed-water or aquafaba. Same process of traditional mayos.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Inclusivity: making a mayonaise that everybody can eat. The use of miso give the mayo more dept an add extra umami. Learn about flavor enhancement and upcycling.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
Lactose Free
Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	288	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	61	(% of total)
Fibre Content	12.2	(grams)
Sodium	1.9	(grams)
Sugars	7.8	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.5	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	3
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Carrot, raw	100	10	100	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	32	10
Cauliflower, raw	100	10	100	2.2	<0.1	2.4	-	25	15
Tempeh, unprepared	100	10	100	6.2	<0.1	0.2	0.7	128	-
Miso, soya, paste	-	1.5	15	6.6	5.1	6	0.7	19.5	-
Oil, rapeseed	-	0.9	9	-	-	-	6.9	80.9	-
Almond, drink, unsweetened	7.6%	0.5	5	0.2	<0.1	0.4	0.1	1.3	-
Lemon, juice, fresh	4.5%	0.3	3	0.3	<0.1	2	-	1.41	-
Salt	-	0.3	3	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Almond and miso mayonnaise	Emulsifying and pasteurizing	4°C for up to 3 days	Dips
	(2) Roasted vegetables	Roasting or baking	4°C for up to 3 days	Hot dishes, snacks and rice salads
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

- (1) Miso mayonnaise:** mix lemon juice, almond milk, salt and miso together with a blender. Add rapeseed oil a little at the time till it thickens and the ingredients all well emulsified.
- (2) Roasted vegetables:** cut the carrots in fingers, cut the cauliflower in florets and slice the tempeh in stripes. Roast the carrots, cauliflower and tempeh on a pan or in the oven with oil till crispy and to taste salt, parsley and lemon juice.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of roasted veggies and tempeh 1 bowl of miso-mayo	Serve vegetables and tempeh hot with miso mayonnaise on the side. For one serving: 200 gr of roasted veggies 100 gr of roasted tempeh 40 gr of miso-mayo	Green food with deep taste from the miso mayonnaise. Goes well as an alternative to meatbased dishes with lots of crispy greens and umami.

Potatoes, curd, linseed oil, raw seasonal vegetable sticks

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dishes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Nürnberg and Essen, Germany

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Classical german kitchen doesn't have to be heavy, sour and sausage. Culinary classes have been seen as having a positive impact in healthy eating behaviours. Handling the knife: peeling and cutting raw veggies is fun and secure, if you know the right technique.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Seasonality every season has it's vegetable suited for being eaten raw.

Progressive exposure the oil can be mixed with the curd or drizzled over the potatoes.

Active learning children can choose the type of veggies they want to taste.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	325	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	19	(% of total)
Fibre Content	6.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.8	(grams)
Sugars	16.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4/5
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Potato, sweet, raw	100	1.75	175	2.4	<0.1	5.5	0.1	159.25	15
Curd, lean	57.1%	1	100	-	<0.1	3.1	-	51	-
Carrot, raw	16%	0.28	28	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	8.96	10
Milk, whole	14.3%	0.25	25	-	<0.1	4.5	2.2	15.25	-
Parsnip, raw	12.6%	0.22	22	4.7	<0.1	5.4	0.2	15.62	10
Parsley, fresh	5.7%	0.10	10	5	<0.1	-	0.1	3.7	-
Chives, fresh	5.7%	0.10	10	2.3	<0.1	-	0.3	6.2	-
Oil, rapeseed	2.9%	<0.1	5	-	-	-	6.9	44.95	-
Lemon, juice, fresh	1.7%	<0.1	3	0.3	<0.1	2	-	1.41	-
Salt	1.1%	<0.1	2	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Oil, linseed	1.1%	<0.1	2	-	-	-	10.1	18	-
Pepper, black/white	0.1%	-	0.2	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	0.66	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Potatoes		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	All kinds of use
(2) Curd		Whisking and seasoning	4°C for up to 3 days	Dips, spreads
(3) Carrot		Peeling and cutting	4°C for up to 3 days	For cooking, salads
(4) Parsnip		Peeling and cutting	4°C for up to 3 days	For cooking, salads
(5) Herbs		Washing and cutting	4°C for up to 3 days	Everything but desserts

DIRECTIONS

(1) **Potatoes** can be prepared in a variety of ways. They can be baked (peeled or unpeeled), smashed after boiling or baking, baked after boiling and smashing, or simply steamed, which preserves the most nutrients, but is also the most boring way. Cut the (2) **seasonal veggies** into a handy format for children to want to reach out and slam dunk into the curd or just eat without making a mess. Mix the linseed oil, herbs and other seasoning into what is originally called "Kräuter-Quark". Even if it reads like a german Hair-Metal-Band, it tastes delicious and the kids will love it.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Container of baked Potatoes, Bowl of Curd mixed with Herbs and Oil	Potatoes go on the curd, not the other way around.	German Soul Food: Food for the Body, Food for Thought.
Container of cut carrots		
Container of extra Parsnip	150 gr of potatoes.	
Container of extra Herbs for Topping	100 gr of curd.	
Bottle of Linseed Oil for extra Topping	50 gr of raw veggies.	While curd provides the proteins the muscles need to grow strong, potatoes and raw veggies are not only chock-full of vitamins and fibre. Potatoes consist of long-chain carbohydrates. These are the fuel for the brain and whole body. Because they form in long chains, they satisfy hunger and give energy for a long time.

Pumpkin cake / Coca de calabaza

TYPE OF DISH

Dessert

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Valencia, Spain

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

By working in the school garden, learning about the seasonality of fruit and vegetables, and introducing pumpkins through progressive exposure.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

This dessert embodies everything we stand for in SchoolFood4Change: It is healthy, sustainable, flavourful and seasonal. Moreover, it is suitable for people with celiac disease, gluten intolerance and lactose intolerance. It is also a versatile recipe as the pumpkin can be replaced by boiled potatoes, as in the original 'coca' from Castelló, and sprinkled with icing sugar.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
Lactose Free
VEGETARIAN
Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	449	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	49	(% of total)
Fibre Content	3.1	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	51	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.7	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Pumpkin, raw	100	0.5	62.5	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	8.75	33
Sugar, brown	80%	0.4	50	-	<0.1	99	-	198	-
Egg, whole, chicken, raw	76.8%	0.38	48	-	0.1	0.2	3.1	63.36	10
Almond, flour	50%	0.25	31.25	5.2	-	0.625	0.41	179	-
Lemon, zest	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Pumpkin puree		Roasting and mashing	4°C for up to 3 days	Any kind of dough (gnocchi, pasta, bread, cookies)
(2) Egg whites		Whipping	Use it straight	Vegetable omelettes, soufflés
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Cut the (1) **pumpkin** in large pieces and roast in at 180°C. Aside, separate the (2) **egg whites** from the yolks, whip the whites until stiff. Meanwhile, mix the rest of the ingredients by mashing the pumpkin with a fork. Better choose a thin skinned pumpkin so that to leave the skin on. Add the whipped albumens and fold into the mixture from the bottom to the top. Place a sheet of baking paper on the baking tray and pour the mixture on top. Bake at 180°C for 25/30 minutes. We can decorate with panela powder or melted chocolate.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of cake	Served on a dessert plate with a fork, but can also be eaten with the hands.	It can be served with fresh fruit.
It can be served in the self-service or buffet line of the dining room	190 gr per portion	

Red curry with vegetables and edamame

TYPE OF DISH

Cereal/bread/potato-based dish

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Copenhagen, Denmark

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Upcycling Enhancement!

Learn about flavor enhancement and upcycling. Go to visit miso productions in Copenhagen. Kind of one off the hottest areas in the moment.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

To have a sauce that goes in every season. It is to give a umami boost for the vegetables plate, but also pairs good with a large range of other products: rice, chicken, fish etc. It is made as a flavor enhancer.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free
Lactose Free
Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	258	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	63	(% of total)
Fibre Content	6.6	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	8.7	(grams)
Saturated Fats	11	(grams)
Plant-based protein	NO	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	4
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (gr)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Coconut, milk	100	6.6	66	0.5	<0.1	1.5	15.2	114.18	-
Carrot, raw	84.8%	5.6	56	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	17.92	10
Pepper, sweet, red, raw	75.8%	5	50	1.8	<0.1	4.3	-	12.5	15
Broccoli, boiled	37.9%	2.5	25	2.7	<0.1	-	0.1	6.75	15
Onion, red, raw	25.8%	1.7	17	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	6.75	10
Oil, olive, extra virgin	7.6%	0.5	5	-	-	-	14.9	45	-
Curry, powder	7.6%	0.5	5	25	<0.1	-	1.6	18.5	-
Lentils, green / brown, dried	7.6%	0.5	5	18	<0.1	1	0.3	15.3	-
Lime	4.5%	0.3	3	2.8	<0.1	1.7	-	1.23	-
Soya, beans, boiled	4.5%	0.3	3	6.5	<0.1	-	0.8	3.69	-
Miso, soya, paste	4.5%	0.3	3	6.6	5.1	6	0.7	3.9	-
Garlic, raw	3%	0.2	2	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	3.16	-
Salt	3%	0.2	2	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Ginger, root	3%	0.2	2	2	<0.1	1.7	0.2	1.62	-
Sugar, brown	3%	0.2	2	-	<0.1	99	-	7.92	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Red curry sauce	Braising	4°C for up to 5 days	Dip, soups and ragout
	(2) Rice	Boiling	4°C for up to 5 days	Salads, bowls, dumplings
	(3) Edamame	Steaming	4°C for up to 5 days	Pestos
	(4) Broccoli	Blanching and roasting	4°C for up to 5 days	Velloutes
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

(1) Red curry sauce: sauté onions and garlic in the oil. Then add ginger and red curry. Afterwards add carrots, red pepper, miso, lentils and Coconut, milk. Let it all simmer for approx 20 min. Then blend it and finish with adding salt, lime juice and sugar for taste. Blanch and roast bouquets of **(4) broccoli** in a pan or in oven. Using the same water of broccoli, boil the **(2) rice**. Steam in oven fresh **(3) edamame** beans. Serve the red curry sauce with hot boiled rice, broccoli and edamame.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 pot of curry sauce 1 pot of cooked rice 1 tray of broccoli and edamame	Serve warm, on a plate or bowl. For one serving: 100 gr of red curry sauce 100 gr of boiled rice 80 gr of veggies	Hot sustainable sauce made from greens Denmark meets Thailand. A dish known to most children, but transformed into a green dish.

Sweet potato ducats with creamy spinach and tempeh cubes

TYPE OF DISH

Vegetable & legumes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Vienna, Austria

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

“Workshop on Legumes & Sweet Potatoes”

Children learn about different protein sources focusing on the different kinds of legumes and which typical dishes from all over the world are prepared from them.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

The dish contains all textures and is colourful. It is also very easy to make vegan, gluten-free and lactose-free. Ingredients are regionally available in organic quality. Plant Based milk is selfmade from seeds.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	386	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	15	(% of total)
Fibre Content	9.3	(grams)
Sodium	0.5	(grams)
Sugars	10	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Potato, sweet, raw	100	16.60	166	2.4	<0.1	5.5	0.1	151	2
Tempeh, unprepared	33.1%	5.5	55	6.2	<0.1	0.2	0.7	70.4	-
Spinach, raw	30.1%	5	50	2	<0.1	-	0.1	13	-
Soy, milk	14.5%	2.4	24	1.1	<0.1	1.7	0.2	6.96	-
Stock, vegetable	8.1%	1.35	13.5	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	0.81	-
Oil, sunflower seed	3.6%	0.60	6	-	-	-	10.6	53.82	-
Flour, wheat, wholemeal	3.6%	0.60	6	10.3	<0.1	5.4	0.3	19.8	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3%	0.5	5	-	-	-	14.9	45	-
Oil, sesame	1.5%	0.25	2.5	-	<0.1	-	14.5	22.45	-
Tamari, sauce	0.8%	0.13	1.25	0.1	4.8	0.6	-	0-5	-
Garlic, raw	0.7%	0.12	1.2	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	1.9	-
Salt	0.6%	0.10	1	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	0.1%	<0.1	0.1	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	0.33	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Tempeh	Marinated + roasted	4°C vacuumed, for up to 3 days	Curry, ragout, sugos
	(2) Spinach sauce	Simmering + blending	4°C vacuumed, for up to 3 days or frozen	Soups and vegetable Lasagne
	(3) Sweet potatoes ducats	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Burgers, soups
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Cut **(1) Tempeh** and marinate it for 3 hours at room temp. Roast the tempeh cubes at a high temperature (200-220°C) for approx. 15 minutes to make them nice and crispy. For the **(3) ducats**, sweet potatoes are cut in round shapes, 0,5 cm thick, brushed with olive oil and are roasted at high temperature (200-220°C) for approx. 15 minutes to create a nice skin. For the **(2) sauce**, cook the spinaches in a light, white roux for approx. 15 mins over a low heat and then blend it. Instead of traditional milk, choose a plant based milk from sunflower seeds.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of roasted sweet potato 1 tray of tempeh 1 tray of spinach sauce	150 gr Sweet potato 50 gr Tempeh 60 gr Spinach sauce	The dish is sweet and crunchy, with no added sugar.

ADAPTABILITY

ALLER
GENS

TEMPERATURE
SERVING

TEXTURE
TEXTURE

FAMILIARITY

MODU
LARITY

SEASONALITY

Cuisine and circularity

Collective catering, particularly in school canteens, is an ideal context for establishing and consolidating the habit of eating balanced and healthy meals. Given the unique characteristics of catering systems, such as the high volume of meals served, their widespread presence throughout the countries and the service offered on a daily basis, these environments now represent both an opportunity in terms of the educational message they convey and a risk of value loss in the food supply chain. When it comes to school canteens, this argument becomes even more relevant, as the target audience is the least inclined to compromise on health and the most demanding in terms of food acceptance.

That is why school canteens today have a mission to minimise both food waste and food loss. It is therefore clear that, while aiming for the acceptance of healthier meals by guiding food preferences, it is still possible to recover waste and optimize the production flow without compromising the final taste.

The recipes presented in this section reflect effective strategies for preventing value loss during the planning of food processing processes or for recycling certain ingredients, giving them added and higher value. Given that meat production and processing are widely known topics and already considered priorities in waste reduction, the following recipes focus mainly on baked goods and fruit and vegetables, the foods that generate the most waste and for which less comprehensive mapping is available.

The recipes proposed here concern:

- the use of the whole ingredient - as in vegetable meatballs and pumpkin and aubergine stew, where, thanks to the educational activity described, you learn how to use every single part of the vegetable, focusing also on the value of “ugly products” that are unappealing to large-scale distribution channels;

- new opportunities from leftovers and by-products, showing how easy it can be to give new value to waste from another production chain through creative recycling, as in the case of **Porridge chips with bean spread** and **Delicious creamy leek soup with herb croutons**;
- simplifying recipes and incorporating camouflage: these two actions combined represent an effective strategy for tackling the general issue of food waste in reverse, starting with one of the most wasted foods: fish. As highlighted in the recipe **Zucchini and white fish patties**, the enhancement of a local ingredient can be guided by the use of a few ingredients processed in a familiar form.

In the context of the recipes presented in this manual, an important consideration emerges regarding the percentage of Kitchen Waste per ingredient, with a specific focus on the potential uses of upcycling processes and other possible applications of semi-processed products. These parameters are key elements to consider when selecting ingredients and their respective processing methods.

You can explore these topics by reading the second chapter, *Progressive Display and Circular Cooking*, of the *School Menu Design Handbook* on pages 77-78 for food waste in school canteens, and pages 88-104 for a discussion of the principles of the circular economy and the approach applied to enhance ingredients in new recipes.

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**Czech
Republic**

Andrea Hruskova, Dagmar Sedlářová,
Tom Václavík

**Delicious creamy leek soup
with herb croutons**

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**Copenhagen,
Denmark**

Søren Buhl Steiniche, Astrid Dahl,
Ebbe Engdal Skovfoged, Emil Kiær
Lund, Christian Rune Jensen

Porridge chips with bean spread

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**Tallinn,
Estonia**

Kadri Ausmaa, Kendra Kairi Vaino,
Kristi Tiido

Pumpkin and aubergine stew

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Slovakia

Eva Blaho, Katarina Medvedova,
Lubos Mego

Vegetable patties

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**Viimsi,
Estonia**

Kadi Bruus, Tina Saar

Zucchini and white fish patties

Delicious creamy leek soup with herb croutons

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Czech Republic

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

The leek and it's family

Workshop on how to prep a creamy soup of different vegetables and cereals of your choice and brainstorming about the family of liliaceae botanical family.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Processing of seasonal vegetables. The creamy consistency of the soup ensures a delicate taste, an attractive consistency for children.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	299	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	49	(% of total)
Fibre Content	8.1	(grams)
Sodium	0.1	(grams)
Sugars	2.2	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2.2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Water	100	3	300	-	-	-	-	-	15
Oregano, dried	13.3%	0.4	40	15	<0.1	-	2.1	144	-
Onions, raw	8.3%	0.25	25	2.7	<0.1	4.5	0.1	9.25	15
Potatoes, raw	8.3%	0.25	25	1.8	<0.1	1	-	22	-
Stock, vegetable	4.2%	0.13	12.5	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	0.75	-
Plant-based alternative to cream based on oat	4.2%	0.13	12.5	0.4	<0.1	1.4	2.1	17	-
Croutons	4%	0.12	12	4	1	3.8	6.7	58.9	-
Millet, raw	3.3%	0.1	10	3	<0.1	-	0.8	37	-
Leek, raw	2%	<0.1	6	3	<0.1	3	-	1.68	-
Oil, olive, extra virgin	0.3%	<0.1	1	-	-	-	14.9	9	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Croutons		Dehydrating in oven	Dry storage for up to 5 days	Herb breadcrumb, thickener for soups
(2) Soup base		Braising (dry + wet cooking) + blending	4°C for up to 3 days	Soup, curry, risottos
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

For the (2) **soup base**, toast finely chopped onions in oil, then add potatoes cut into small cubes, boiled millet and vegetable broth. Cook for 15 minutes. Finally, add the finely chopped leeks and cook for another 5 minutes. Blend the soup and soften it with oat cream.

For the herb (1) **croutons**, cut whole grain toasted bread into small cubes, spread on a baking sheet with baking paper and pre-bake in the oven at 180°C for 4 minutes.

Mix the oil with the herbs, then pour it onto the crouton tray, mixing thoroughly to coat all the pieces. Bake for another 4 minutes until golden.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 big pot/tray of soup base 1 tray of croutons	Serve immediately after preparation for the best flavor and texture. Portion weight: 500 gr Serving temperature: warm. Serving tools: serve in a deep plate with a spoon. Type of service: buffet or plate service.	This dish is ideal for vegetarian or vegan menus and caters well to individuals seeking plant-based meals.

Porridge crisps with bean spread

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Copenhagen, Denmark

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

To show pupils how to upcycle leftovers from breakfast and incorporate with baked vegetables for a healthy afternoon snack.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Schools often have leftovers from breakfast club. This recipe gives an opportunity to upcycle this to a filling snack full of protein and umami from the beans and sundried tomatoes.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	125	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	35	(% of total)
Fibre Content	5.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.1	(grams)
Sugars	2.3	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	8
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Beans, white, boiled	100	0.72	36	9.9	<0.1	0.6	0.2	40.7	-
Carrot, raw	55.6%	0.4	20	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	6.4	100
Oatmeal	19.4%	0.14	7	7.3	<0.1	2	1.3	26.11	100
Tomatoes, dried tin/glass, drained	16.7%	0.12	6	8	0.5	6.3	1.5	11.82	-
Sunflower, seeds	13.9%	0.1	5	7.4	<0.1	-	6	32.35	-
Tomato, puree, concentrated, tinned	13.9%	0.1	5	3.7	0.3	12.9	-	4.35	-
Lemon, juice, fresh	6.3%	<0.1	2.25	0.3	<0.1	2	-	1.05	-
Garlic, raw	1.3%	<0.1	0.45	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	0.711	-
Pepper, black/white	1.1%	<0.1	0.4	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	1.328	-
Salt	1.1%	<0.1	0.4	-	33.8	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Bean spread		Blending	4°C for up to 3 days	Sandwiches
(2) Porridge crisp		Dehydrating in oven	Dry storage	Warm as a puré
(3)				
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

For the **(1) bean spread**, toast the Sunflower, seeds lightly on a dry pan. Then put Sunflower, seeds, cooked carrots and beans, garlic, tomato puree, salt and lemon juice in a food processor and blend until you have a uniform creamy mass. Season thoroughly with salt, pepper and extra lemon juice or vinegar. Add little by little the liquid from the beans until the consistency is creamy.

For the **(2) porridge crisp**, cook the oatmeal in salted boiling water for 15 mins while stirring. The mass should thicken without being too dense. If too thick, dilute with water. Blend the mass, spread it thinly on baking paper and bake for 45 min at 150°C degrees. Let the oat crisps to cool and break into suitable pieces.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 bowl of bean spread 1 tray of porridge crisps	Serve at room temperature. As a self serve or in small individual snack servings.	Creamy and filling dip and crisps. Upcycling breakfast leftover into snack.

Pumpkin and aubergine stew

TYPE OF DISH

Stew & ragout

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Tallinn, Estonia

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

Winter

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Introduction to various pulses:

- Younger age group - characterize different legumes (beans, lentils and peas- find similarities and differences (color, shape).
- Older age group - find the nutritional value of different pulses per 100 g and compare with food of the same nutritional value from the food pyramid.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

Encourage school chefs to use local ingredients (pumpkin, tomato) along with less popular foods (eggplant) and to use different flavor combinations. Also both main ingredients - eggplant and pumpkin - are the ingredients that you can use whole.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

Lactose Free

Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	775	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	34	(% of total)
Fibre Content	14.7	(grams)
Sodium	0.6	(grams)
Sugars	6	(grams)
Saturated Fats	1.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Stock, vegetable	100	15	150	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	9	-
Rice, basmati	100	15	150	1.3	<0.1	-	0.2	528	-
Pumpkin, raw	40%	6	60	1	<0.1	1.7	0.1	8.4	-
Aubergine/eggplant, raw	40%	6	60	2	<0.1	3	-	12	5
Tomatoes, classic, round, raw	26.7%	4	40	1.3	<0.1	2.9	0.1	8	-
Lentils, green / brown, dried	20%	3	30	18	<0.1	1	0.3	91.8	-
Beans, white, boiled	20%	3	30	9.9	<0.1	0.6	0.2	33.9	-
Onion, red, raw	13.3%	2	20	2.5	<0.1	5.2	0.1	7.4	15
Lime	6.7%	1	10	2.8	<0.1	1.7	-	4.1	50
Oil, olive, extra virgin	3.3%	0.5	5	-	-	-	14.9	45	-
Soy, sauce	1.3%	0.2	2	0.1	4.8	0.6	-	0.8	-
Chilli, powder	1.3%	0.2	2	22	<0.1	-	2.9	7.46	-
Oregano, dried	1.3%	0.2	2	15	<0.1	-	2.1	7.2	-
Cumin, seed, dried	1.3%	0.2	2	10.5	0.2	-	1.9	8.54	-
Paprika, powder	0.7%	0.1	1	20.9	<0.1	-	1.7	3.59	-
Coriander	0.7%	0.1	1	-	-	-	-	<0.1	-
Cinammon	0.7%	0.1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Eggplant		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Baba ganush
(2) Pumpkin		Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Pumpkin puree, pumpkin soup and risottos
(3) Rice		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Pilau rice
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

Poke the **(1) eggplants** with the tines of a fork, cut them in halves lengthwise and brush with olive oil. Roast in oven until very tender. Once chilled, cut into large pieces.

Cut the **(2) pumpkin** skin on into large pieces and roast in the oven.

For the stew base, peel the onions and cut into stripes. Heat olive oil a saucepan and toast until golden. Add cooked eggplants, pumpkin, lentils and beans. Then add tomatoes and season with Soy, sauce, chili powder, oregano and the spices. Stir to combine, then pour in the stock. Bring to the boil, then turn down the heat to very low. Cover with a lid and cook for 1½ hrs, checking and stirring every 15-20 mins to prevent it from burning. Stir in the lime juice and taste for seasoning, serve hot with boiled **(3) rice**.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
2 GN trays one for stew, other for rice	Portion size: 150 gr boiled rice and 250 gr pumpkin-aubergine stew. Also suitable for serving with flatbread or corn chips.	Best serving on flat plate, fork or spoon needed.

Vegetable patties

TYPE OF DISH

Patties & galettes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Budapest, Hungary

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

Spring

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Sad vegetables

“Sad carrot didn’t want to leave the farm because it was afraid it would end up as food waste. The wise chef then came up with a beautiful recipe for her that all children like. And that’s exactly patties”.

Could you make up stories and recipes for vegetables that are also afraid to leave the farm because they think they are unpopular?

Carrot stems and leaves are highly versatile and can be used in a variety of ways instead of being discarded. From leaves you can prepare pesto or herbal garnish or use them even for the smoothies, or directly to our patties. Carrot Stems can be added to the stock. If you truly have no use for them, they make excellent additions to compost.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

This recipe teaches the preparation of vegetable-based patties, emphasizing the use of fresh vegetables and grains for a balanced, meat-free dish. It promotes sustainable, healthy eating habits suitable for children and adults.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	206	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	59	(% of total)
Fibre Content	4.2	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	4.9	(grams)
Saturated Fats	2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	12
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Cauliflower, raw	100	4	40	2.2	<0.1	2.4	-	10	10
Cabbage, green, raw	60%	2.4	24	4.1	<0.1	4.1	-	8.64	-
Carrot, raw	60%	2.4	24	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	7.68	-
Bread, crumbs	57.5%	2.3	23	4.6	0.6	5.2	0.7	86.94	-
Egg, whole, chicken, raw	31.8%	1.27	12.7	-	0.1	0.2	3.1	16.76	-
Milk, whole	30%	1.2	12	-	<0.1	4.5	2.2	7.32	-
Oatmeal	20%	0.8	8	7.3	<0.1	2	1.3	29.84	-
Cheese, Parmigiano Reggiano	10%	0.4	4	-	1	-	17.6	16.16	15
Oil, olive, extra virgin	6.3%	0.25	2.5	-	-	-	14.9	22.5	-
Salt	0.4%	<0.1	0.15	-	33.8	-	-	-	10
Garlic, raw	0.3%	<0.1	0.1	2.1	<0.1	1	0.1	0.15	20
Pepper, black/white	0.1%	<0.1	0.05	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	0.16	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Oat porridge		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Fillings for other different recipes, vegetable or meat patties
(2) Vegetables		Boiling	4°C vacumed for up to 5 days or in a clean container for 3 days	Pureed soups, vegetable stews or starchy side dishes
(3) Vegetable patties		Baking	4°C for 3 days or freeze not baked for up to 3 months	Filling for wraps or a vegan casserole
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

(1) **Oat porridge**: cook the oat in milk to make a thick porridge.

(2) **Boiled vegetables**: clean the cabbage, cauliflower, and root vegetables.

Cook them in salted water until tender.

Combine: Mash the cooked vegetables, then mix them with the oat porridge, grated cheese, eggs, minced garlic, and spices. Season with salt.

(3) **Form the patties**: add breadcrumbs to thicken the mixture if needed.

Shape the mixture into patties.

Cook: bake the patties in the oven until golden brown.

Serve: serve warm with a side salad or dipping sauce.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
<p>Serving tools Plate with a fork and knife</p> <p>Service type Buffet or plated, alongside a salad or dip. Patties can be served as a side dish with a salad or roasted vegetables for a complete meal or dipping sauce</p>	<p>Portion weight: 110 gr</p> <p>Service: Serve immediately after baking for the best crispness and texture.</p> <p>Holding: If necessary, keep warm in an oven or hot holding station before serving.</p>	<p>The patties are a vegetarian option that is both nutritious and flavorful. They pair well with light salads or can be served as a main course with a grain side.</p>

Zucchini and white fish patties

TYPE OF DISH

Patties & galettes

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Tallinn, Estonia

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Feedback from school chef training revealed that a lot of local Estonian fish food is wasted in schools, which is a very large amount for children in our maritime country. We encouraged chefs to use more creativity. During the training, we practiced using fewer ingredients, focusing on innovative techniques and seasonings to achieve 0 waste while maintaining the good taste, appearance, and value of the food. Thanks to red lentils, we got a better color for the colorless cutlets and the round shape invites children to eat them more.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

We encourage school cooks to use simpler vegetables with fish in their meals to get children used to eating more vegetables as well a local Estonian lake fish. We added just 2 vegetable, zucchini and lentils to the fish, which are also left over in large quantities. But using these ingredients together as cutlets made the result more acceptable to children, because children love round cutlets. Schoolchefs liked the idea and the design.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

Lactose Free

VEGETARIAN

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	545	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	31	(% of total)
Fibre Content	23.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.7	(grams)
Sugars	6.5	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.6	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	11
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	NO
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Lentils, green/brown, dried	100	10	100	18	<0.1	1	0.3	306	-
Pike, fish, boiled	50%	5	50	-	-	-	-	-	20
Courgettes, raw	50%	5	50	0.9	<0.1	2.3	0.1	9	5
Buckwheat, groats	50%	5	50	5.6	<0.1	2.1	0.4	178.5	-
Lettuce, romaine, raw	30%	3	30	2.1	<0.1	1.2	-	5.1	-
Carrot, raw	30%	3	30	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	9.6	-
Pepper, sweet, red, raw	30%	3	30	1.8	<0.1	4.3	-	7.5	-
Bread crumbs (with onion powder)	7%	0.7	7	4.6	0.6	5.2	0.7	26.46	-
Salt	2%	0.2	2	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	1%	0.1	1	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	3.32	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
(1) Fish Cutlets		Steaming + mixing + roasting	Freezing of 4°C for up to 3 days	Burgers
(2) Fermented veggies		Brining and sitting room temp	4°C for up to 6 days	Versatile side dishes, fillings
(3) Buckwheat mush		Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Stews, soups
(4)				
(5)				

DIRECTIONS

(2) Ferment carrot, zucchini and red bell pepper with sea salt and apple cider vinegar and keep under pressure for 24 hours.

For the (1) cutlets, mix cooked pike fish, boiled lentils and grated raw zucchini.

Season with salt, white pepper and dill.

Form 160g cutlets (100g net weight) and bread them in breadcrumbs and onion powder.

To get healthy and a gold and crispy crust, bake the cutlets in a preheated oven at 190°C for about 13 minutes. Suitable for serving both warm and cold.

Cook buckwheat in salted boiling water (or steam it) to obtain a sort cornmeal mush.

Serve the cutlets with buckwheat mush and salad and fermented veggies tacos.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 tray of cooked patties 1 tray of buckwheat mush 1 tray of fermented vegetable salad tacos	100 gr patties 120 gr cooked buckwheat mush 80 gr veggie tacos	The pupils come and chooses the food, the customer service representative serves a portion according to the specified quantity to each diner separately.

UPCYCLING

WHOLE
INGREDIENT

CAMOU
FLAGE

SEMI
FINISHED
PRODUCT

FOOD
CIRCULARITY

WASTE
PREVENTION

Dishes for advanced tastes

The sixth chapter concludes the collection of recipes and, following a circular path, returns to the first chapter, recalling the fundamental concepts of 'good' and 'acceptance'. At the beginning of this collection, it was stated that individuality and personal experience play a significant role in each person's judgement of taste or distaste. However, even in this case, an evidence-based approach will be adopted to focus on those ingredients or preparations that are often rejected and, consequently, difficult to accept over time.

In this perspective, it is important to emphasise that the acceptability of a specific recipe or dish is determined by familiarity and the importance of a gradual and structured approach for school children.

The following recipes have a high potential for developing adverse reactions or disgust in children, while providing appropriate solutions.

In particular, attention will be paid to certain types of preparations:

- **soups:** the characteristic feature of this type of preparation is the moist cooking of the ingredients, which results in a warm, broth-like consistency. Due to the presence of floating solid pieces, soups are known to be difficult to accept. It is advisable to achieve a creamy consistency (make sure you have starchy vegetables on your shopping list!) which can be combined with crunchy elements such as croutons and toasted seeds. In addition, it is advisable to add flavour through aromatic bases such as soffritto: toasting finely chopped vegetables at the beginning of the preparation will provi-

de a rounded umami sensation. Finally, the long cooking process on the one hand ensures the concentration of flavours, but on the other hand can lead to an undesirable brownish colour, especially in vegetables. Blanching can help prevent this;

- **salads:** these dishes may be underrated when considered only as a side dish, but they can become appetising when considered as a recipe in their own right. They are the perfect place to apply the concept of biodiversity: crispy leaves of different sizes, colours and flavours, combined with a variety of legumes and grains and garnished with seeds and nuts. Condiments, herbs and fermented products are all further possibilities to characterise the mix. Finally, giving students the opportunity to choose from a wide variety of these elements can really make a difference.

You can explore these topics by reading the first chapter *Food Preferences* of the *School Menu Design Handbook* pages 6↔12 for understanding how the senses work in determining food acceptability, pages 19↔53 for an insight on how sensory properties and processes techniques can create the goodness.

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Umeå,
Sweden

Jonathan Nyberg, Mirella Persson,
Maria Svensson, Thomas Videhjarta

Broccoli soup

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Budapest,
Hungary

Andras Bittsanszky, Eszter Faki,
Éva Kinorányi, Orsolya Diófási-Kovács

Bulgur salad with chickpeas

208

Malmö,
Sweden

Helen Nilsson, Louise Dahl Gottberg,
Tina Bowley, Andrea Razzaboni

Fish soup with seasonal toppings

212

Umeå,
Sweden

Jonathan Nyberg, Mirella Persson,
Maria Svensson, Thomas Videhjarta

Sunny soup

216

Czech
Republic

Andrea Hruskova, Dagmar Sedlářová,
Tom Václavík

Supersalad with Beluga lentils

220

Budapest,
Hungary

Andras Bittsanszky, Eszter Faki,
Éva Kinorányi, Orsolya Diófási-Kovács

Tuscan vegetable soup

Broccoli Soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Umeå, Sweden

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

This weeks vegetable

We present information in our “tasting station” based on vegetables such as broccoli, with the purpose to teach the kids more about the vegetable and to experience it through the tasting.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

One of the most popular dishes in Umeå. By camouflaging lentils into this soup we get a nutritious and healthy soup which is also accepted by the pupils.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	338	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	26	(% of total)
Fibre Content	5.8	(grams)
Sodium	0.4	(grams)
Sugars	8.7	(grams)
Saturated Fats	7.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	10
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Milk, whole	100	66	120	-	<0.1	4.5	2.2	73.2	-
Potatoes, raw	33.3%	22	40	1.8	<0.1	1	-	35.2	-
Broccoli, boiled	25%	16.50	30	2.7	<0.1	-	0.1	8.1	-
Carrot, raw	25%	16.50	30	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	9.6	-
Macaroni	25%	16.50	30	3	<0.1	1	0.2	106.8	-
Leek, raw	16.7%	11	20	3	<0.1	3	-	5.6	-
Cream, whipped	16.7%	11	20	-	<0.1	3.1	23	67.8	-
Lentils, red	8.3%	5.5	10	18	<0.1	1	0.3	30.6	-
Stock, vegetable	0.8%	0.55	1	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	<0.1	-
Salt	0.8%	0.55	1	-	33,8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	0.3%	0.22	0.4	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	1.32	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Rooted vegetables	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Pasta sauce or stew
	(2) Soffritto	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Versatile in its composition, it fits any cooked dish
	(3) Pasta	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads and frittatas
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Sauté the **(2) soffritto** of onion, carrot and celery.
 Add water/stock, a mix of **(1) rooted vegetables**, grated potato and lentils and bring to a boil.
 Boil it all together. then add the dairy products and finally the chopped broccoli.
 Mix to a smooth texture and season to a good taste. Thicken with cornstarch if needed.
 Optional, serve it warm with boiled "short" **(3) pasta**.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Serve in gastronome containers	One bowl of soup per person with the possibility to have more if they want. 3 dl per portion.	Serve with freshly baked bread or crispy topping like croutons or roasted seeds.

Bulgur salad with chickpea

TYPE OF DISH

Salad

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Budapest, Hungary

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

SUMMER

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Salad Preparation for elder pupils

Elder students will prepare a fresh salad by washing, slicing, and arranging vegetables. This task teaches safe knife handling, promotes healthy eating habits, and encourages independence in the kitchen.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

Chickpeas are an excellent source of protein. Salad, as a meal form, offers a range of nutrients and flavors while supporting sustainable eating habits.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	287	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	49	(% of total)
Fibre Content	12	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	3.2	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.8	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	8
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Chickpeas, boiled	100	5	50	3.8	0.2	0.25	-	70	-
Bulgur, wheat, raw	100	5	50	6	-	0.2	-	170	-
Tomatoes, classic, round, raw	60%	3	30	0.5	-	0.36	-	6	10
Cucumber, skin, raw	60%	3	30	0.6	-	-	-	3.9	10
Pepper, California	60%	3	30	0.5	-	-	-	7.5	10
Onions, raw	10%	0.5	5	0.1	-	0.21	-	1.85	15
Lemon, juice, fresh	10%	0.5	5	-	-	-	-	2.35	-
Oil, olive, extra-virgin	6%	0.3	3	-	-	-	2	27	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Bulgur	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups, vegetable stews or alongside starchy side dishes
	(2) Seasonal vegetables	Slicing	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads and fillings
	(3) Sauce	Stirring	4°C for up to 3 days	Salads, bruschette
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Cook the **(1) bulgur** in salted boiling water, then let it chill after pouring a drizzle of Oil, olive, extra-virgin to prevent clumping. Aside, prepare **(2) seasonal veggies**, dicing tomatoes, cucumbers, peppers and onions into equal pieces. Rinse and drain canned chickpeas. Prepare a **(3) sauce** mixing together Oil, olive, extra-virgin, Lemon, juice, fresh, grated garlic, salt, pepper and chopped green parsley. In a large mixing bowl or pot, combine the cooked bulgur and chickpeas with the raw vegetables. Pour over the sauce and mix thoroughly to coat all ingredients.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 bowl or tray of salad 1 bowl of extra sauce	Served chilled. If you want, put a crunchy dressing to the top (e.g. toasted chickpeas, toasted bread). 250 gr per portion.	This is a high fibre containing food. It can also be made gluten-free if you use another gluten-free alternative grain instead of bulgur.

Fish soup with seasonal toppings

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Malmö, Sweden

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Foraging for pesto

Since ramson is very common in Skåne the kids can pick it outside themselves and make the pesto together with the teacher or cook in the classroom using the ingredients and a mortar.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

The swedish guidelines for nutrition says that we should eat fish at least twice a week. To reach this goal we have to make the flavours familiar and not only serve fried fish.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

GLUTEN FREE

LACTOSE FREE

Vegetarian

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	562	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	14	(% of total)
Fibre Content	3.6	(grams)
Sodium	0,6	(grams)
Sugars	4.4	(grams)
Saturated Fats	6.2	(grams)
Plant-based protein	NO	
Polyunsaturated fats	NO	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	5
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Cod, raw	100	1	100	-	<0.1	-	0.1	75	-
Plant-based alternative to cream based on oat	90%	0.9	90	0.4	<0.1	1.4	2.1	122.4	-
Croutons	50%	0.5	50	4	<0.1	3.8	6.7	245.5	-
Potatoes, raw	20%	0.2	20	1.8	<0.1	1	-	17.6	-
Carrot, raw	10%	0.1	10	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	3.2	-
Onion, raw	10%	0.1	10	2.4	<0.1	4.1	0.1	3.1	10
Celery, raw	10%	0.1	10	1.1	<0.1	1	-	1.4	-
Remson	10%	0.1	10	2.5	-	-	-	3	-
Oil, sunflower seed	5%	<0.1	5	-	-	-	10.6	44.85	-
Oil, rapeseed	5%	<0.1	5	-	-	-	6.9	44.95	-
Lemon, juice, fresh	2%	<0.1	2	0.3	<0.1	2	-	0.94	-
Horse-radish, raw	1%	<0.1	1	7.5	-	7.3	0.1	0.8	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Vegetables	Roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Minestrone, stir-fry or every kind of soup
	(2) Ramson Pesto	Mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Can be used as dressing
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Dice carrots, celery and spring onion, and toast them in rapeseed oil.

Cut the potatoes in large cubes and add them to the sauteed vegetables.

Pour in water and season with preferred herbs, salt and pepper. When **(1) vegetables** are fully cooked, add cream and cubes of cod. Leave the fish in the hot stew without stirring and serve directly. Blend together ramson, horseradish, Lemon, juice, fresh and oil and get to a pesto texture. Top the stew with **(2) ramson pesto** and croutons.

Depending on the season you can change the vegetables, remove the cream and change the main ingredient in the pesto. From that you will have four different seasonal fish stews.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Bowl of pesto, bowl of croutons and a pot with stew	It can be served with different toppings and children can choose themselves. One serving is 300 gr.	The base can be made from many different vegetables, tomatoes in the summer, pumpkins in the autumn for example. The pesto can be made from basil in the summer, ramson in spring and kale in the winter.

Sunny soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Umeå, Sweden

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

AUTUMN

WINTER

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Sunny Soup Canva

Sunny soup is a very versatile concept. Pupils can decide how to complexify this recipe by adding colors, shapes, textures and aromas over the times as it would be an ongoing canva to be drawn.

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

One of the Umeå most popular dishes and loved by children. It has a round and semi-spicy taste and a colour that is appreciated by the students.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

Gluten Free

LACTOSE FREE

VEGETARIAN

Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	729	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	23	(% of total)
Fibre Content	31	(grams)
Sodium	0.5	(grams)
Sugars	8.2	(grams)
Saturated Fats	11.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	8
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	NO

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Red, lentils	100	71.5	130	18	<0.1	1	0.3	397.8	-
Carrot, raw	57.7%	41.25	75	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	24	-
Coconut, cream	50%	35.75	65	0.5	<0.1	1.5	15.2	112.4	-
Vegetable, minced	38.5%	27.5	50	8.9	0.5	2	0.2	74	-
Potatoes, raw	30.8%	22	40	1.8	<0.1	1	-	35.2	-
Plant-based alternative to cream based on oat	26.9%	19.25	35	0.4	<0.1	1.4	2.1	47.6	-
Onions, raw	15.4%	11	20	2.7	<0.1	4.5	0.1	7.4	-
Oil, rapeseed	2.3%	1.65	3	-	-	-	6.9	27	-
Stock, vegetable	1.2%	0.83	1.5	0.1	0.3	0.2	-	<0.1	-
Garlic, powder	0.8%	0.55	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tumeric	0.6%	0.44	0.8	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chilli, powder	0.6%	0.44	0.8	22	<0.1	-	2.9	2.98	-
Salt	0.4%	0.28	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Curry	0.2%	0.11	0.2	25	<0.1	-	1.6	0.74	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Vegetable base	Braising (dry + wet cooking) + mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Pasta sauce or stew
	(2)			
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Prepare a (1) **vegetable base** sautéing chopped onions with curry and turmeric spices. Add carrots, potatoes and vegetable broth (or water) and bring to a boil. Let it simmer until the root vegetables are soft. Add lentils and coconut cream. Boil it all together until everything is soft. Mix to a smooth texture and season to a good taste.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Serve in gastronome containers	One bowl of soup per person with the possibility to have more if they want. 3 dl per portion.	Serve with freshly baked bread och crispy topping like croutons or roasted seeds.

Supersalad with Beluga lentils

TYPE OF DISH

Salad

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Czech Republic

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Omega 3 Quiz

Learning about different types of legumes and seeds and also their nutritional value, e.g. omega 3 (any other legume and seed can be used in the dish).

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

> why I am preparing this dish

The use of fresh seasonal ingredients and how to minimally process them in order to preserve their nutritional profile.

This dish is ideal for vegetarian or vegan menus and caters well to individuals seeking plant-based meals.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- Vegetarian

VEGAN

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	513	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	48	(% of total)
Fibre Content	14.1	(grams)
Sodium	0.2	(grams)
Sugars	3.1	(grams)
Saturated Fats	4.4	(grams)
Plant-based protein	YES	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	YES
Organic	NO
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Lentils, green/brown, dried	100	27.5	50	18	<0.1	1	0.3	153	-
Potatoes, raw	100	27.5	50	1.8	<0.1	1	-	44	15
Bugle, salad	100	27.5	50	1.7	-	-	0.1	14.8	-
Rocket, raw	100	27.5	50	1.9	<0.1	-	0.1	11	-
Radish, raw	100	27.5	50	0.9	<0.1	3	-	11	5
Pumpkin, seeds	40%	11	20	8.5	<0.1	1.6	11.1	114.8	-
Oil, pumpkin	30%	8.25	15	-	-	-	10.1	135	-
Plant-based alternative to cream based on soya	30%	8.25	15	0.5	<0.1	1.2	3	24.15	-
Vinegar, cider, apple	15%	4.13	7.5	-	<0.1	0.6	-	1.65	-
Mustard	3.4%	0.94	1.7	3	1.4	2.7	0.4	2.19	-
Salt	1%	0.28	0.5	-	33.8	-	-	-	-
Pepper, black/white	1%	0.28	0.5	26.4	<0.1	-	0.7	1.66	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Beluga lentils	Boiling	4°C for up to 3 days	Soups and dahl
	(2) Potatoes	Cook and roasting	4°C for up to 3 days	Potato salad, gratins
	(3) Mustard dressing	Mixing	4°C for up to 3 days	Burgers and sandwiches
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Rinse and boil **(1) Beluga black lentils** in salted water for 20 minutes.
 Boil the **(2) potatoes** and once chilled cut them into slices and toast them in a pan.
 Add lentils and salt.
 Mix in a bowl rocket salad, bugle and radishes cut into circles. Once chilled, add potatoes and lentils.
 Aside, prepare a dressing by mixing pumpkin oil, apple cider vinegar, mustard and vegetable cream.
 Season the salad with **(3) mustard dressing**, pumpkin oil and dry roasted pumpkin seeds.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
1 big tray of salad 1 bowl with mustard dressing	Serve immediately after preparation for the best flavor and texture. Serving temperature: cold. Serving tools: deep plate or bowl and fork. Type of service: buffet or plate service.	Pumpkin seeds are suitable for self-service.
	300 gr per portion.	

Tuscan vegetable soup

TYPE OF DISH

Soup

WHERE RECIPE IS SERVED

Budapest, Hungary

SEASON(S) OF THE DISH

Autumn

Winter

SPRING

Summer

RELATED EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Sprouting root vegetables:

- Cut off the top 1,5 cm of the turnip
- Place the cut parts on damp cotton wool
- Place in a warm place in the window, keep the cotton wool moist
- The fresh parsley is ready

KEYWORDS AND COMMUNICATED VALUES

>why I am preparing this dish

The vegetable content of the soup is high and the vegetables used are familiar to children. Cheese is an extra source of protein and a umami boost to make it more round.

INCLUSION AND ALLERGENS

> for whom I am preparing this dish

- Gluten Free
- Lactose Free
- VEGETARIAN**
- Vegan

HEALTHY: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE PER PORTION

Nutritional Value	42	(kilocalories)
Fruit and Vegetables	95	(% of total)
Fibre Content	2.9	(grams)
Sodium	<0.1	(grams)
Sugars	2.33	(grams)
Saturated Fats	0.8	(grams)
Plant-based protein	NO	
Polyunsaturated fats	YES	

SUSTAINABLE: ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL PROFILE

Main Ingredients	6
Upcycling Processes	NO
Organic	YES
Biodiverse/Traditional	YES
Within a 200 km radius	YES

Ingredients <small>NEVO database was used for the ingredient names and nutritional information associated with each one</small>	Parametric Percentage	Quantity per Batch (kg)	Quantity per Portion (gr)	Nutritional Value per Portion					Kitchen Waste (%)
				fibre (gr)	sodium (gr)	sugars (gr)	sat. fat (gr)	energy (kcal)	
Kale, curly, raw	100	3	30	4.7	<0.1	0.4	0.1	9.9	15
Carrot, raw	100	3	30	2.8	<0.1	4.2	0.1	9.6	10
Celery, stalk	66.7%	2	20	1.1	<0.1	1	-	2.8	10
Turnip, raw	33.3%	1	10	2.7	<0.1	4.6	-	3.1	10
Tomatoes, round, raw	33.3%	1	10	1.3	<0.1	2.9	0.1	2	10
Cheese	16.7%	0.5	5	-	0.6	-	13.7	15.1	-

PREPARATION	Semi Finished	Key Process Elements	Conservation/Storage	Other Possible Uses
	(1) Vegetables	Braising (wet +dry cooking)	4°C for up to 3 days	Vegetable bulgur, salads, rice balls
	(2)			
	(3)			
	(4)			
	(5)			

DIRECTIONS

Heat oil over medium-high heat. Add onion and toast, stirring often, for 3-4 minutes until very soft. Add carrots, celery, turnip. Keep on stirring for 4-5 minutes until (1) **vegetables** begin to soften. Pour in stock, spices and tomatoes. Cover and bring to the boil over medium-high heat. Reduce heat and simmer, stirring occasionally, for 30-35 minutes. Add kale and simmer for 5 minutes or until leaves are soft. Serve soup with grilled bread and cheese.

SERVICE LINE	RECEPTION INFORMATION	NOTES FOR THE SERVICE
Pot or cauldron	Served in deep plate with spoon 300 ml/ portion.	This is a high fibre containing food. Grilled sourdough bread and grated cheese, to serve.

SOUPS

SALADS

**REDUCE
ADVERSE
REACTIONS**

FLAVOUR

**FAMILIARITY
FAMILIARITY**

**ACCEP
TANCE**

**SELF-DETERMINED
CHOICES**

Conclusion and thanks

by Fassio Franco, Povigna Carol, Bigi Matteo, Buracco Nabuel, Tecco Nadia

Special thanks to the people from 12 European countries who contributed

The University of Gastronomic Sciences is grateful to all the cook trainers and municipalities, that took part in designing and collecting recipes for a healthy diet for school children across Europe.

We would also like to thank all the SchoolFood4Change partners who supported this task.

This recipe handbook is not merely a collection of dishes intended for European school canteens—it is a true tool for cultural, educational, and gastronomic transformation. The result of a collective effort involving chefs, nutritionists, educators, public administrators, and researchers from 12 European countries, this handbook embodies an integrated vision of school food as a driver of change.

The 42 recipes included here have been designed not only to meet nutritional and environmental standards but also to serve as tools for communication, education, and inclusion.

Each dish has been conceived to be accessible, replicable, and adaptable, taking into account children's food preferences, specific dietary needs, the seasonality of ingredients, and the sustainability of supply chains.

By applying principles such as circular cooking, protein transition, biodiversity enhancement, and waste reduction, the handbook promotes a systemic approach to school food. The recipes become a meeting point between culinary knowledge, nutritional science, sensory education, and environmental responsibility.

Furthermore, the manual is intended as a practical resource for all stakeholders involved in school catering: chefs, dietitians, teachers, educators, parents, and

public administrators. Each recipe is accompanied by detailed sheets illustrating its nutritional value, environmental information, preparation and serving methods, as well as possible connections with educational activities and classroom workshops.

We hope this work will inspire new practices in school canteens, fostering a constructive dialogue between cooking, education, and sustainability. Because every meal served at school is an opportunity to nourish not only the body, but also the soul, raise awareness, and influence the future of the next generations.

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4.2
DELIVERABLE

RECIPE HANDBOOK

Università di Scienze
Gastronomiche di Pollenzo
University of Gastronomic of Pollenzo

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